

Left atrial parameterisation and multi-modal data analysis: application to atrial fibrillation

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Abstract / Resumen

Abstract. Many aspects related to the pathogenesis and progression of atrial fibrillation (AF or AFib), the most common type of arrhythmia, are still not fully understood. Besides, current AF treatments, such as ablation strategies, have shown sub-optimal success rates showing the need of developing novel research approaches and computational methodologies. Non-invasive imaging techniques, such as late-gadolinium magnetic resonance imaging (LGE-MRI), have recently emerged as powerful tools to identify structural changes of atrial tissue allowing patient-specific strategies, and extending ablation approaches from generic techniques (e.g. pulmonary vein isolation (PVI)) to substrate-based approaches. Atrial fibrosis imaging using LGE-MRI can be used to improve the understanding of the underlying mechanisms of atrial structural remodeling, contributing significantly to understand the pathophysiology and progression of AF.

In order of application, the first contribution of this thesis is an automatic framework to segment the left atrium from LGE-MRI data. The method is based on a whole-heart multi-atlas segmentation scheme that benefits from a shape-based atlas selection strategy to identify the most convenient set of atlases, prior to registration, avoiding the high computational cost of the latter.

Second, a framework for obtaining a standardised two-dimensional representation of the left atrial cavity that simplifies data inspection and allows comparison of different atria. Unfolding methods, such as conformal flattening, applicable to the cardiac ventricles are not suitable for the atria due to the complex nature of the constraints (i.e. fixed position of the pulmonary veins and left atrial appendage holes). With our method, auricular cavities of any shape can be mapped to a 2D standardised representation in a few seconds.

Third, a methodology to detect and measure the incompleteness of ablation lesions after PVI. PVI stops the fibrillation by ablating the surroundings of the PV avoiding the transmission of the abnormal electrical signals that cause AF and are frequently originated in the veins. The procedure is known to fail in many cases, possibly due to the appearance of gaps in the ablation lesion leading to re-connection. Currently, there is no standard and observer independent way of assessing the magnitude of the gap. Using graph theory, we have provided a unique definition of the gap and a way of quantifying its magnitude, which is highly reproducible and may help in predicting the outcome of PVI.

Finally, we have applied the previously mentioned tools and other computational techniques to real clinical datasets showing how our methods can be transferred and included into clinical research practice. We have investigated the regional distribution of ablation gaps in a cohort of AF patients who undergone radiofrequency PVI, the reproducibility of scar imaging with LGE-MRI, the intra- and inter-observer variability of manual LA segmentation tools, the preferential regional distribution of fibrosis in AF patients, and the relation between electroanatomical information (e.g. voltage) and LGE-MRI data.

Resumen. Muchos aspectos relacionados con la patogénesis y la progresión de la fibrilación auricular (FA), el tipo más común de arritmia, son todavía desconocidos. Además, los tratamientos actuales, como la ablación auricular, presentan tasas de éxito subóptimas mostrando la necesidad de desarrollar nuevos enfoques de investigación y de implementar nuevas técnicas computacionales. Técnicas de imagen no invasivas, como la resonancia magnética cardíaca con realce tardío de gadolinio (RMC-RTG), han surgido recientemente como valiosas herramientas para identificar cambios estructurales en el tejido auricular. Esto permite extender estrategias de ablación genéricas como, por ejemplo, el aislamiento de las venas pulmonares y desarrollar técnicas específicas para cada paciente que tengan en consideración el tipo de sustrato. La visualización de fibrosis auricular con RMC-RTG puede utilizarse para mejorar la comprensión de los mecanismos subyacentes del remodelado estructural auricular, contribuyendo significativamente a comprender la fisiopatología y la progresión de la FA.

En orden de aplicación, la primera contribución de esta tesis es un método automático para segmentar la aurícula izquierda a partir de imágenes de RMC-RTG. Se basa en un esquema de segmentación multi-atlas de todo el corazón y utiliza una estrategia de selección de atlas basada en la morfología auricular para identificar el sub-conjunto de atlas más apropiado antes del registro, evitando el alto coste computacional de este último.

En segundo lugar, un método para obtener una representación bidimensional estandarizada de la cavidad de la aurícula izquierda que facilite la inspección de datos y permita la comparación de diferentes aurículas. Los métodos de desplegamiento, como el “conformal flattening”, utilizados con los ventrículos cardíacos no son directamente aplicables a las aurículas debido a lo complejo de sus restricciones: los orificios de las venas pulmonares y de la orejuela deben tener una posición fija. Con nuestro método, las cavidades auriculares de cualquier forma pueden ser transformadas en mapas bidimensionales estandarizados en pocos segundos.

En tercer lugar, una metodología para detectar y medir la incompletitud de las lesiones tras el aislamiento de las venas pulmonares (PVI, por sus siglas en inglés). PVI detiene la fibrilación mediante la ablación del entorno de las venas pulmonares evitando la transmisión de las señales eléctricas patológicas causantes de la FA (frecuentemente originadas en las venas). Es sabido que el procedimiento falla frecuentemente, posiblemente debido a la recuperación del tejido provocando la aparición de agujeros (gaps) en la lesión de ablación y posteriormente reconducción eléctrica. Actualmente

no existe una forma estándar e independiente del observador de evaluar la magnitud de los gaps. Utilizando la teoría de grafos, hemos proporcionado una definición inequívoca de gap y una forma de cuantificar su magnitud, que es altamente reproducible y puede ayudar a predecir el resultado de la PVI.

Finalmente, hemos aplicado las herramientas mencionadas anteriormente y otras técnicas computacionales a conjuntos de datos clínicos reales que muestran como nuestros métodos pueden transferirse e incluirse en la investigación clínica. Hemos investigado la distribución regional de gaps en un grupo de pacientes con FA que se sometieron a PVI por radiofrecuencia, la reproducibilidad de la visualización de cicatriz con RMC-RTG, la variabilidad intra- e inter-observador de herramientas manuales de segmentación de la aurícula izquierda, la distribución regional de fibrosis en pacientes con FA, y la relación entre información electroanatómica (por ejemplo, voltaje) y datos de RMC-RTG.

Preface

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Contents

Acronyms	xvii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Research context	2
1.2 Contributions	8
1.3 Outline of the thesis	9
2 Left atrial segmentation from LGE-MRI combining multi-atlas whole heart labeling and shape-based atlas selection	11
2.1 Introduction	13
2.2 Methods	14
2.3 Experiments and Results	17
2.4 Discussion	19
2.5 Conclusions	20
3 Fast quasi-conformal regional flattening of the left atrium	21
3.1 Introduction	23
3.2 Methods	25
3.2.1 Flattening pipeline	25
3.2.1.1 LA cavity extraction	25
3.2.1.2 Boundary and regional constraints definition	25
3.2.1.3 Fast Regional Flattening (FRF)	28
3.2.2 2D template definition	31
3.3 Experiments and Results	35
3.3.1 Distortion analysis of 2D templates	35
3.4 Clinical applications	38
3.4.1 Gap quantification.	39

3.4.2	Inspection of the relation between EAM and LGE-CMR data	40
3.5	Discussion	40
3.6	Conclusion	43
A	Appendix. Shape metrics.	45
B	Appendix. Additional flattening examples.	47
4	Quantification of incomplete ablation lines after pulmonary vein isolation	49
4.1	Introduction	51
4.2	Methods	54
4.2.1	Left atrial segmentation and tissue characterisation . .	56
4.2.2	Semi-automatic parcellation of the LA	57
4.2.3	Graph-based gap identification and quantification . . .	60
4.2.4	Multi-threshold result integration	62
4.3	Experiments and Results	63
4.4	Discussion	65
4.5	Conclusion	67
5	Clinical applications	69
5.1	Gap quantification population analysis	71
5.2	Reproducibility of post-ablation atrial scar LGE-CMR imaging	78
5.3	Preferential regional distribution of fibrosis in patients with AF	89
5.4	Analysis of the intra- and inter-observer variability of LGE-CMR measurements	95
5.5	Multi-modal data joint analysis	103
5.5.1	Analysis of the influence of radiofrequency ablation parameters on permanent lesion formation	103
5.5.2	Inspection of the relation between regions of slow electrical conduction and regions of scar in the LA	109
6	Conclusions	113
6.1	Future research lines	115
	Bibliography	117
	Curriculum Vitae	xxiii

Publications

xxv

List of Figures

1.1	Atrial Fibrillation illustration	3
1.2	Illustration of the mechanism maintaining AF.	4
1.3	AHA guidelines for AF treatment	5
1.4	Illustration of pulmonary vein isolation	6
1.5	SUM 3D/2D templates and examples.	7
2.1	Scheme of the LA segmentation pipeline	15
2.2	Cluster representatives	17
2.3	LA segmentation results	18
3.1	Overview of proposed flattening method	26
3.2	Constraints recomputation.	28
3.3	Example of different quasi-conformal LA flattenings.	29
3.4	Zoom of PV holes region after flattening	31
3.5	Summary of shape measurements	34
3.6	Distortion analysis performed using the 3D SUM template	36
3.7	Summary of distortion metrics using 15 left atria.	37
3.8	Flattening examples of 3D LA with different synthetic texture patterns on the surface.	38
3.9	Examples of clinical applications of FRF.	39
B.1	Flattening examples using different synthetic textures.	47
B.2	Examples of flattened LA with projected LGE-CMR intensity.	48
B.3	FRF maps corresponding to EAM and LA segmentations from LGE-CMR data.	48
4.1	Gap quantification pipeline	53
4.2	Definition of gap searching areas	57
4.3	Gap definition	58
4.4	Example of gap detection	58

4.5	Example of distance maps	59
4.6	Example of <i>RGM</i> estimation on synthetic data	61
4.7	Gap quantification in clinical data	64
4.8	Multiple scar thresholds combination	64
4.9	Number of gaps and <i>RGM</i> variability	66
5.1	Population gap quantification results	73
5.2	Histograms of the RGM_{NAUC}	73
5.3	Regional distribution of gaps results	74
5.4	Flowchart of scan acquisitions	80
5.5	Illustration of pulmonary vein encirclement computation.	83
5.6	Examples of raw images and corresponding scar shells for a single subject.	84
5.7	Impact of time from GBCA administration and reproducibility of PVE measurements	85
5.8	Reproducibility of pulmonary vein encirclement measurements.	86
5.9	Relationship between percentage PVE and electrical reconnection.	87
5.10	Pipeline for regional fibrosis quantification	90
5.11	Proposed parcellation of the template LA.	91
5.12	Results of the regional distribution of left atrial fibrosis	93
5.13	Inter-observer shape differences.	97
5.14	Scar overlap quantification	98
5.15	Example of pair-wise scar overlap measurements.	100
5.16	Congruence of LA 3D shape and scar overlap.	101
5.17	Dice vs. area of scar comparison	102
5.18	Multi-modal data analysis framework	104
5.19	Multi-modal data example using the SUM.	107
5.20	Example of pair of SUMs generated.	109
5.21	Scheme of multi-modal data analysis.	110
5.22	Examples of EAM vs LGE-CMR spatial correspondence	111
5.23	Normalized image intensity vs conduction velocity comparison.	112
6.1	Inspection of RF parameters	116

List of Tables

2.1	Results of the LA segmentation from LGE-MRI	19
A.1	Shape metrics: ostia perimeters	45
A.2	Shape metrics: inter-seed distances	45
5.1	Gap quantification results	72
5.2	Nomenclature of the image acquisitions	82
5.3	Regional fibrosis quantification results	92
5.4	Intra- and inter-observer variability results	101
5.5	Example of multi-modal numerical analysis.	108
5.6	Complete multi-modal numerical analysis.	109

Acronyms

AF	Atrial Fibrillation
EAM	Electroanatomical Map
EPS	Electrophysiological Study
GBCA	Gadolinium-Based Contrast Agent
HD	Hausdorff Distance
LA	Left Atrium/Atria
LAA	Left Atrial Appendage
LGE-CMR	Late Gadolinium Enhanced Cardiac Magnetic Resonance
LGE-MRI	Late Gadolinium Enhanced Magnetic Resonance Imaging
LIPV	Left Inferior Pulmonary Vein
LSPV	Left Superior Pulmonary Vein
MAS	Multi-Atlas Segmentation
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MV	Mitral valve
PAAS	Post-Ablation Atrial Scar
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PV	Pulmonary Vein
PVI	Pulmonary Vein Isolation
RIPV	Right Inferior Pulmonary Vein
RSPV	Right Superior Pulmonary Vein
WHS	Whole-Heart Segmentation

Introduction

The global aim of this thesis is to explore and develop computational techniques to analyse different types of images and information for a better understanding of the pathophysiology and progression of atrial fibrillation.

1.1 Research context

Atrial fibrillation (AF), sometimes called “the growing epidemic”, is the most frequent type of arrhythmia. AF prevalence increases with ageing and its incidence is rapidly growing due to the increasing life expectancy in developed countries. Although not being life-threatening by itself, it increases risk for stroke and heart failure. Patients with AF may suffer chest pain, palpitations, shortness of breath, dizziness, or fatigue, while others may not experience symptoms at all (“silent” AF), complicating its diagnosis.

The left atrium (LA) is one of the two upper chambers of the heart, it receives oxygen-rich blood from the lungs through the pulmonary veins (PV) and pumps it into the left ventricle through the mitral valve (MV). From there, the oxygenated blood is distributed to the whole body. LA anatomy is highly variable and it involves the main cavity, the PV, the left atrial appendage (LAA) and the MV. The most variable parameter is the number of PV, with almost 70% of people having 4, while the rest having 3, 5 or 6. The LAA also exhibits high shape variability across people. The thickness of the LA wall varies locally ranging from less than 1 mm to 3 mm, slightly thicker than the wall of the right atrium but considerably thinner than the cardiac ventricular wall.

AF appears when abnormal electrical signals cause the LA to beat rapidly and irregularly, preventing blood from flowing properly through the cardiac chambers (see Figure 1.1). There are three different types of AF: paroxysmal, persistent, and long-standing persistent (chronic or permanent). Paroxysmal AF refers to temporal episodes of AF that stop on their own or after treatment in less than seven days. Persistent AF lasts more than seven days and it only stops with treatment, and long-standing AF is ongoing for many years and cannot be corrected.

Mechanisms underlying the appearance and maintenance of atrial fibrillation are still not fully understood, but it is recognised that ageing and diseases such as hypertension, heart failure, and ischaemic heart disease coexist with AF in the ample majority of patients. The main hypothesis

Figure 1.1: Atrial fibrillation illustration¹. Normal heart on the left and AF heart on the right.

is that a combination of ectopic foci and reentry of the activation wave around an anatomic obstacle (e.g. fibrosis or scar patches) create the underlying conditions for AF (see Figure 1.2). Related to the ectopic foci theory, pulmonary veins are recognised as the most frequent triggers of AF since it has been demonstrated that the tissue connecting PV and LA body is responsible for creating and propagating the pathological signals that disrupt normal heart rhythms in AF (Haissaguerre et al., 1998). Additionally, subject specific sources of AF are being investigated and experimental and growing clinical evidence indicates that rotors can be key players in AF maintenance. Rotors are the patterns of electrical activation in which the activation wavefront rotates around a fixed or a moving point. Rotors generate waves that propagate through the myocardium and interact with anatomic and functional obstacles leading to fibrillatory conduction, fragmentation, and new wavelet formation (Pandit and Jalife, 2013; Quintanilla et al., 2016). Narayan et al. (2012) showed for the first time that physiologically guided computational mapping revealed sustained electrical rotors and repetitive focal beats during human AF. Although rotors are apparently similar to reentry around a region of scar, the two mechanisms are quite different (Krummen et al., 2015): in a reentry around a scar patch, the obstacle is passive and the surrounding reentrant circuit is the princi-

¹Source: <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2190988>

Figure 1.2: On the left, illustration of 3 basic concepts of the mechanism maintaining AF: multiple circuit re-entry (A), focal-ectopic drivers (B), and rotor sources (C). On the right, schematic of the relation between basic understanding and clinical approaches. The multiple wavelet theory of atrial fibrillation (A) led to the highly-successful surgical maze procedure (B). Attempts to reproduce surgical maze by catheter ablation largely failed (C). Clinical identification of the key role played by the pulmonary veins (PVs) led to the first truly successful ablation procedures for AF (D) and to basic studies of the underlying mechanisms (E). Limited success of PV ablation for persistent AF led to a detailed examination of other mechanisms and mechanism-targeted procedures (F). RA = right atrium. Illustrations adapted from Nishida et al. (2014).

pal mechanism maintaining AF; on the other hand, rotors are the principal mechanisms and the surrounding spiral waves disorganize and fuse passively with the milieu. Related to the re-entry hypothesis, it has been shown that fibrosis, i.e. the formation of excess fibrous connective tissue in an organ or tissue in a reparative or reactive process (called scarring when it appears in response to injury (e.g. cardiac ablation)), interferes with the normal conduction of the electrical signals in the heart. Importantly, all the evidences and theories are compatible with the concept that a small number of localised high-frequency electrical activation sources can maintain AF for long periods of time (Quintanilla et al., 2016).

The observed heterogeneity in AF pathogenesis and maintenance also suggests different optimal treatments. Guidelines from the American Heart Association (AHA) can be seen in Figure 1.3. The first option often consists

1.1. RESEARCH CONTEXT

in antiarrhythmic and anticoagulation drugs to control heart rate and to help preventing blood clots, respectively. If antiarrhythmic medication fails (drug-refractory AF) cardiac ablation is frequently used. In AF ablation, clinicians seek to permanently interrupt pathological electrical conduction within the atria to restore normal sinus rhythm by scarring (through cardiac catheterizations) the heart tissue that generates abnormal electrical signals. Other AF treatments are: synchronized cardioversion, where an electric shock is administered to the sedated patient who will after that convert into normal sinus rhythm, surgical maze (or Cox maze) procedure, where surgical incisions are made to create lesions that will heal into scars that disrupt conduction, and pacemaker implantation.

Figure 1.3: American Heart Association (AHA) diagram guidelines for atrial fibrillation treatment.

Pulmonary vein isolation (PVI) ablation, usually preferred to surgical treatment being less invasive, remains the cornerstone in drug-refractory AF treatment. As mentioned before, PVs are important triggers in AF and PVI, aiming to create a continuous scar lesion that completely encircles

(a) Catheter ablation for AF treatment (source: <https://www.stopafib.org>) (b) PVI using radiofrequency energy (left) or cryoballoon (right). Picture from Calkins et al. (2017).

Figure 1.4: Illustration of pulmonary vein isolation (PVI).

the veins (see Figure 1.4b), stops activation waves from propagating to the atrial body. However, and independently of the ablation technique used (radiofrequency, laser, cryoballoon), PVI success rate remains suboptimal (30-50 % on the long term) and several repeated procedures (redos) are often required. Various reasons have been hypothesised for the high AF recurrence rate after PVI as for example inadequate initial therapy or re-conduction recovery (PV reconnection) due to the presence of gaps in the ablation lines. Without durable PVI, it is unclear if other ablation strategies such as ablation of stable electrical rotors (Focal Impulse and Rotor Modulation (FIRM)) that has already shown to improve ablation outcome compared with conventional ablation alone (Krummen et al., 2015), are required.

Late-gadolinium enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (LGE-MRI) has recently demonstrated its capability to visualise regions of fibrosis and scar in the LA myocardium and might provide insight into the progress of AF. It has also been used to identify ablation gaps after PVI that, as explained before, may have a role in PV reconnection as demonstrated by Kowalski et al. (2012) who showed how MRI identified gaps were more likely to become electrically reconnected.

Inspection of the LA characteristics (e.g. shape, wall thickness, tissue type (healthy or scar), ablation gaps, etc.) from 3D LGE-MRI volumes often requires the segmentation of the LA as a first step. Fusion of several manual LA segmentations is considered the gold standard but it is time consuming and it lacks intra- and inter-observer reproducibility. Multi-atlas segmentation (MAS) techniques have been used to automatically segment diverse

structures from different sort of images. The general pipeline in MAS involves registering a set of atlases (labeled images) to the to-be-segmented image and combining the resulting labels through label fusion. Many different techniques can be used in the two main steps of the pipeline which often includes atlas selection as a pre- or post-registration step to identify the most convenient set of available atlases, reducing computational time and potentially increasing segmentation accuracy. Very recently, novel fully automatic segmentation techniques based on convolutional neural networks (CNN) have been proposed with promising results (Xiong et al., 2018).

New mapping techniques providing high density electric maps allow localisation of potential AF sources (rotors and foci). During an electrophysiological study (EPS), the mapping system captures the electrical information in the LA endocardium and creates electroanatomical maps of the left atria.

Visual inspection of 3D data is time consuming and multi-modal comparison tedious and inaccurate. Flattening methods permit to visualize the whole structure in a single view and to put into correspondence different data if the 2D map is standardised. Only one method has been proposed to unfold the LA in a consistent way, Williams et al. (2017), who recently proposed the Standardised Unfold Map (SUM): a pair of templates (3D LA shape and its corresponding 2D flat representation) was defined with known point correspondence (see Figure 1.5). The unfolding of an arbitrary LA surface mesh involves registering it to the 3D template, projecting the to-be-mapped information from the registered arbitrary LA to the 3D template, and transferring this information to the 2D map using the known 3D-2D point-to-point mapping. 24 LA regions were defined on the template, which allows local comparison across different LA.

Figure 1.5: SUM 3D/2D templates (left) and 2 examples of local activation time (LAT) (center) and late gadolinium enhancement (LGE) (right) mapping. Illustration adapted from Williams et al. (2017).

Clinical research performed in the hospitals often comprises manual steps that are associated to human errors, lack of reproducibility and high work-

load. In this thesis, we aimed to provide tools to consistently analyse data acquired in clinical practice in an automatic or semi-automatic reproducible way. This reduces the amount of time required to analyse clinical data and it produces reproducible metrics. Our tools would provide more insight into AF pathophysiology, progression and outcome of current treatments.

1.2 Contributions

This thesis presents the following contributions:

- A novel atrial flattening methodology where a quasi-conformal 2D map of the LA is obtained in a fast and lost-less framework. While cardiac ventricles have an established standard representation (e.g. bull's eye plot), the 2D visualization of the LA is more challenging due to its sub-structural complexity including the pulmonary veins and the appendage. Quasi-conformal flattening techniques have been successful to represent information from cardiac ventricles in 2D, however, estimating a quasi-conformal map for the left atria, where constraints are required to place the pulmonary veins and the appendage in the same geometrical 2D location for different cases, is challenging. Using anatomical measurements in a clinical dataset of human LA, we derived a template that best represents the relative locations of the appendage and pulmonary veins, minimizing the distortion, and providing good visualization for the data. The proposed framework is illustrated on synthetic LA surfaces, patient MRI datasets and electroanatomical maps, whereupon we demonstrate how it can be used for patient comparison.
- A novel methodology to semi-automatically quantify incomplete ablation patterns after PVI. First, we proposed an unambiguous definition of gap as the shortest portion of healthy tissue surrounding the PV, and an objective index, the Relative Gap Measure, which represents the portion of the vein not encircled by scar. Additionally, our method provides a full characterization of the gaps in terms of their number, position and length. With the aim of reducing the influence of the scar segmentation process, we proposed a multi-threshold scheme for scar segmentation and the integration of results into a single figure-of-merit.

- An automatic LA segmentation framework based on a multi-atlas segmentation scheme and a shape-based atlas selection strategy. We proposed a two-step strategy to identify the most appropriate set of atlases for segmenting highly variable structures such as the LA. In our framework, a simple sampling approach is able to capture LA morphology and is used to automatically group together similar shapes. Shape information is used to discard bad atlases prior to registration avoiding a high number of computationally expensive registrations and improving segmentation results.
- Other computational techniques were proposed showing how they can be incorporated into clinical practice with the aim of gaining more insight into AF characteristics and treatment: (1) we inspected the regional distribution of ablation gaps in a population of AF patients showing that the left superior PV was more prone to lesion gaps while the left inferior PV tended to have less gaps; (2) we investigated the influence of imaging parameters in the reproducibility of LGE-CMR imaging concluding that post ablation atrial scar imaging is a reproducible finding; (3) we inspected the preferential regional distribution of fibrosis in pre-ablation AF patients showing that fibrosis is predominantly located in the posterior wall around left inferior PV; (4) we quantified the intra- and inter-observer variability of scar detection using manual LA segmentation techniques concluding that measurements were reproducible and can be applied in clinical practice after minimal training of the operator; and (5) we developed registration-based frameworks to inspect the relation between electroanatomical information and LGE-CMR data showing how regions of slow electrical conduction spatially correlate well with regions with atrial scar.

1.3 Outline of the thesis

After this introductory chapter, the rest of the thesis is organised as follows.

Chapter 2. This chapter presents a framework to automatically segment the left atria from LGE-MRI data. It combines multi-atlas whole heart labeling and a shape based atlas selection technique. Experiments were carried out in the context of the international 2018 Atrial Segmentation Challenge.

Chapter 3. In this chapter, we propose a standardised two-dimensional representation of the left atria comparable to the well-known bull’s eye plot of the cardiac ventricles. We show how our method can be used to flatten any type of LA surface such as acquired from MRI, or EAM from electrophysiological mapping systems enabling multi-modal or multi-patient comparison.

Chapter 4. This chapter presents a framework to quantify incomplete ablation lines after pulmonary vein isolation. We provide a consistent definition of ablation gap and propose a method to semi-automatically quantify the completeness of the lesions produced by the PVI procedure. We propose the Relative Gap Measure (*RGM*) to estimate the percentage of gap around a vein, which is defined as the ratio of the overall gap length and the total length of the path that encircles the vein. Additionally, an advanced version of the *RGM* has been developed to integrate gap quantification estimates from different scar segmentation techniques into a single figure-of-merit.

Chapter 5. In this chapter, we present clinical applications of the methods described before and outline other related techniques from a more practical point of view. We show the results of our ablation gap quantification technique on a population of AF patients and show how the *RGM* metric can be used to inspect the reproducibility of post-ablation atrial scar detected with LGE-MRI. We also inspect the reproducibility of manual segmentations of the LA and the measurements derived from them (e.g. scar extent and location). Standardisation technique allows us to consistently compare data from different patients or from different acquisition techniques and the last part of this chapter shows two related applications: we present a method to inspect the preferential regional distribution of natural fibrosis in patients with AF, and two frameworks to inspect the relation between EAM and LGE-MRI data from the same patient.

Chapter 6. This chapter summarizes the most important ideas and contributions of this thesis. Lastly, we propose future research directions.

**Left atrial segmentation
from LGE-MRI combining
multi-atlas whole heart
labeling and shape-based
atlas selection**

Abstract – Segmentation of the left atria (LA) from late gadolinium enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (LGE-MRI) is challenging since atrial borders are not easily distinguishable in the images. We propose a method based on multi-atlas whole heart segmentation and shape modeling of the LA. In the training phase we first construct whole heart LGE-MRI atlases and build a principal component analysis (PCA) model able to capture the high variability of the LA shapes. All atlases are clustered according to their LA shape using an unsupervised clustering method which additionally outputs the most representative case in each cluster. All cluster representatives are registered to the target image and ranked using conditional entropy. A small subset of the most similar representatives is used to find LA shapes with similar morphology in the training set that are used to obtain the final LA segmentation. We tested our approach using 80 LGE-MRI data for training and 20 LGE-MRI data for testing obtaining a Dice score of 0.842 ± 0.049 .

This chapter is adapted from:

Nuñez-García, M., Zhuang X., Sanroma G., Li L., Xu L., Butakoff, C., and Camara, O. *Left atrial segmentation combining multi-atlas whole heart labeling and shape-based atlas selection*. In International Workshop on Statistical Atlases and Computational Models of the Heart (STACOM) 2018. Accepted.

2.1 Introduction

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most frequent type of arrhythmia affecting around 1% to 2% of the worldwide population (approximately 33 million in 2015). Prevalence of AF doubles with each decade of age and the AF incidence is rapidly growing with the increasing life expectancy in developed countries (Andrade et al., 2014; Vos et al., 2016).

Inspection of LA anatomy in clinical routine often involves LA segmentation which is typically done by fusing several manual segmentations. This is the most accurate method nowadays but automatic segmentation is desirable in order to reduce the high workload and to eliminate inter- and intra-observer variability attributable to manual segmentation. However, accurate automatic segmentation of the LA is challenging due to the high variability of atrial shapes: global features such as size and sphericity, and local features such as number, position and orientation of the pulmonary veins (PVs), and size and shape of the left atrial appendage (LAA) greatly differ between patients. Most of patients have 4 PVs (up to 70%) but it is relatively frequent to have a common left trunk (around 15 %) or one or even two extra right PVs (Prasanna et al., 2014). The LAA size and shape could be even more arbitrary (García-Isla et al., 2018).

Some methods have been able to successfully segment the LA in an automatic or semi-automatic way using different image modalities (Chen et al., 2018; Depa et al., 2010; Tao et al., 2016; Tobon-Gomez et al., 2015). LA automatic segmentation is especially challenging in LGE-MRI data due to the intrinsic characteristics of this image modality. LGE-MRI is used to visualize and quantify the extent of fibrosis (or scar) in the chambers of the heart. The contrast agent appears enhanced (white) in fibrotic areas while the myocardium is nulled in the rest facilitating the detection of scar but at the same time complicating the delineation of the cardiac substructures. In the case of the LA, the healthy (non-fibrotic) parts of the thin atrial wall exhibit a very similar intensity profile to the surrounding structures (e.g. the left ventricle).

Multi-atlas segmentation (MAS) has been widely used in different clinical contexts (Iglesias and Sabuncu, 2015). The outline of MAS involves registering N atlases (labeled images) to a given target image and derive the final segmentation by applying label fusion. Many methods have been proposed for the different steps (mainly registration and label fusion) and when the number of available atlases is increased the pipeline often involves atlas se-

lection, i.e. selecting the most appropriate set of atlases and discarding the rest (Sanroma et al., 2014). Ideally, atlas selection needs to be done before the registration step to avoid unnecessary computational costs of registering bad atlases that marginally contribute to the final segmentation (Langerak et al., 2013). On the other hand, this strategy is not optimal neither since registration quality should have a role on atlas selection (e.g. better registration quality for a given atlas). Most MAS schemes rely on registration to a common reference space were similarity metrics can be computed. However, when the population of images shows large variability in appearance and shape it becomes arduous to come up with a unique template that is representative of all the rest. As mentioned before, different LAs often do not even have the same parts (i.e. different number of PVs) and for example, a LA with an extra right PV will not be well represented using a template image with 4 PVs. Thus registration between LAs with varying topology becomes problematic.

In the absence of a suitable common reference space and to avoid a high number of pairwise registrations, we propose to group the training dataset by the corresponding LA morphology, determined from the LA shape. When a new target image has to be segmented, the images from the training set representative of each morphology cluster are registered to the target to identify the correct morphology of the target. Once the morphology is known, the segmentation is carried out via multi-atlas framework using only the atlases corresponding to this morphology. We tested our method using the dataset provided by the organizers of the 2018 Atrial Segmentation Challenge (STACOM'18²). It comprises 100 3D MRI patient data acquired using a clinical whole-body MRI scanner and the corresponding LA manual segmentations.

2.2 Methods

The pipeline of the proposed method can be seen in Figure 2.1. We built our method from the multi-atlas whole-heart segmentation (MAS-WHS) technique presented by Zhuang et al. (2015) and Zhuang and Shen (2016) since the joint segmentation of surrounding structures may help in identifying the structure limits. Briefly, in the registration step of the MAS-WHS strategy all atlases were registered to the target image using a hierarchical scheme

²<http://atriaseg2018.cardiacatlas.org/>

Figure 2.1: Scheme of the proposed pipeline. The cluster representative is depicted enhanced. MAS-WHS = Multi-atlas whole heart segmentation; PDM = Point distribution model; PCA = Principal component analysis; AA = Aux atlases; GA = Global atlases; SA = Specific atlases.

designed for cardiac images: first, a global affine registration was performed followed by a three-level locally affine registration (LARM) (Zhuang et al., 2010) to initialize substructure alignment, and by a non-rigid registration based on free-form deformations (FFD) (Rueckert et al., 2002) to refine local details. We considered seven substructures: left and right ventricular cavities, right atrial cavity, left atria (considering the cavity, the PVs and the LAA), the left ventricular myocardium, the ascending aorta and the pulmonary artery. For the label fusion step we applied atlas ranking based on conditional entropy (Zhuang et al., 2015) and a patch based strategy (Zhuang and Shen, 2016).

To obtain labels of the remaining substructures (i.e. derive whole heart LGE-MRI atlases) we first performed MAS-WHS using the 30 high-resolution balanced steady state free precession (bSSFP) volumetric MRI atlases distributed by the Left Atrial Segmentation Challenge (STACOM’13) (Tobon-Gomez et al., 2015). Due to the intrinsic differences between the two image modalities (LGE-MRI and bSSFP MRI for target and atlases, respectively) the automatic MAS-WHS results were poor for many cases. For that reason we re-segmented all cases applying again MAS-WHS using a new atlas set, Aux Atlas (AA), built selecting the best 15 results obtained in the initial

step and replacing the LA automatic segmentation by the ground truth provided by the STACOM'18 challenge.

To group together images with similar LA shapes we first extracted all LA surfaces from the ground truth segmentations by applying the marching cubes algorithm. After that, we characterized each atrial mesh using a point distribution model (PDM) obtained by consistently sampling the LA surface meshes defining rays from the LA center of mass in all directions. We used spherical coordinates, (r, ϕ, θ) , to define the rays with $r = 100$, high enough to intersect the LA shape, $\phi \in [0, \pi]$ with $\phi/70$ step and $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ with a variable number of samples for each ϕ increasing from 1 to 70 and decreasing again to 1. We proceed like that to have more points in the areas where LA shapes are wider. In that way, the final number of points representing each shape was 2452. The LA shapes were then characterized by the intersection points between the rays and the surface. When the ray intersected more than once (because of the PVs) only the furthest intersecting point was considered. We computed the mean PDM and aligned all the PDMs to the mean using iterative closest point (ICP). Finally, we applied PCA to reduce the dimensionality of the data and clustered the shapes using the Affinity Propagation method (Frey and Dueck, 2007). This method clusters data by iteratively identifying a subset of representative examples and assigning the remaining elements to a specific representative when the method converges. Let us call the set of N cluster representatives global-atlases (GA). Ideally, the GA set contains a good representation of highly variable atrial shapes.

To segment an unseen target image we proceeded as follows: we first registered the GA to the target image using the hierarchical registration scheme commented before (Zhuang et al., 2015). We then ranked all atlases according to the negative conditional entropy of the target image (I) given the warped label image (L_n) which corresponds to:

$$-H(I|L_n) = \sum_{i \in I, l \in L_n} p(i, l) \log \frac{p(i, l)}{p(l)} \quad (2.1)$$

where H is entropy, $p(i, l)$ is the joint probability of the intensity value i and label l , and $p(l)$ is the marginal probability of label l . We then selected the P global atlases with highest negative conditional entropy and found the S closest shapes in PCA space to each of the P GA. The set of $M = P \times S$ atlases defined a target-specific set of atlases (SA) used to derive the final LA segmentation in a MAS framework.

Figure 2.2: All cluster representatives (left) and examples of small clusters showing all pertaining shapes superimposed (right). Representatives are sorted according to the first principal component that was identified as size/sphericity. RSPV = Right Superior PV, RIPV = Right Inferior PV, LSPV = Left Superior PV, LIPV = Left Inferior PV, LAA = Left Atrial Appendage.

2.3 Experiments and Results

We used data from the 2018 Atrial Segmentation Challenge (STACOM'18) to test our method. The dataset was randomly split into training and testing sets (80 and 20 cases, respectively) and, consequently, 80 LGE-MRI whole heart atlases were constructed. PDMs were built using 2452 rays, which was experimentally found appropriate to capture atrial anatomy, and a PCA model describing the LA shape variability in the training set was obtained. We decided to keep the 34 first principal components since they correspond to the 95% of cumulative variance. Fifteen representative shapes were identified by applying the Affinity Propagation clustering method and the GA was built using the corresponding atlases. The mean number of samples in each cluster was 5.33 ± 3.94 ranging from only 1 to 14. The 15 shape representatives can be seen in Figure 2.2 as well as some of the clusters found. Our shape-based clustering method was able to identify a duplicated sample which was eliminated from the dataset. We decided to keep the $P = 3$ best GA as shape representatives and search for the $S = 5$ samples closest to each representative. We therefore constructed the SA with only 15 atlases.

To test segmentation accuracy we used three metrics: Dice similarity defined as

$$Dice(X, Y) = 2 \frac{|X \cap Y|}{|X| + |Y|} \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.3: From left to right: Dice score, surface to surface distance and Hausdorff distance. All distances are reported in mm. Results corresponding to the different sets of atlases considered are shown: AA = Aux Atlases, GA = Global Atlases, SA_s = Specific Atlases found using the preliminary shape, SA = Specific Atlases selected using the proposed approach.

surface to surface distance, defined as

$$S2S(S, T) = \text{mean}(d(S, T), d(T, S)) \quad (2.3)$$

and Hausdorff distance defined as

$$HD(S, T) = \max(d(S, T), d(T, S)) \quad (2.4)$$

where X and Y are the automatic and reference segmentation, respectively, S and T the set of voxels in the boundary of X and Y , respectively, and d is the Euclidean distance.

We compared our shape-based atlas selection approach with the performance obtained using other atlas sets. As baseline we used the results from the MAS-WHS performed using AA. We also derived a preliminary segmentation using the GA since those atlases were already fully registered to the target image in a previous step. We applied label fusion and obtained a preliminary LA segmentation whose related LA surface mesh was then sampled and projected to PCA space. The closest shapes were selected and a new set of target-specific atlases (SA_s) was established. We decided to keep the 15 closest shapes to have same atlas size as in our proposed approach. We investigated if including the highly variable (in terms of LA shape) global atlases, i.e. GA, was beneficial or disadvantageous.

As can be seen in Figure 2.3 and Table 2.1 the best configuration corresponded to solely using the SA. The worse performance corresponded to the use of GA, and whenever the GA was used jointly with the specific atlases SA or SA_s the results got worse than using only the latter.

Table 2.1: LA segmentation results: Dice, surface to surface distance (S2S) and Hausdorff distance (HD) corresponding to the different experiments.

	<i>AA</i>	<i>GA</i>	<i>GA + SA_s</i>	<i>SA_s</i>	<i>GA + SA</i>	<i>SA</i>
Dice	0.807 ± 0.076	0.797 ± 0.122	0.819 ± 0.094	0.828 ± 0.065	0.838 ± 0.075	0.842 ± 0.049
S2S	3.675 ± 1.892	3.553 ± 3.014	3.209 ± 2.231	2.820 ± 1.262	2.843 ± 1.768	2.630 ± 1.124
HD	30.456 ± 16.114	27.442 ± 12.831	26.806 ± 12.215	24.704 ± 8.383	26.014 ± 9.561	24.041 ± 8.141

2.4 Discussion

Results show that the highly variable *GA* was not able to produce accurate segmentations. This could be understood since if the atlas set is very diverse only few atlases will positively contribute to segment each target image, i.e. the number of useful atlases is actually small. Even if in the label fusion step the weight of bad atlases is low, they would still negatively contribute to the segmentation. We found 2 clusters with only 1 representative which means that their shape was so specific that could not be grouped together with other samples. Due to the relatively low accuracy of segmentations with *GA*, the preliminary shapes were inaccurate and quite similar between them. This was also revealed by the fact that after sampling, all corresponding PDMs were very similar, projections to PCA space fell close together and the *SA_s* was (apart from the order) the same in most cases.

However, we found that registering *GA* to the target image and ranking the atlases according to the negative conditional entropy helped to position the target in PCA space and in that way infer shape features such as size or number of PVs. Then, for refinement, we decided to keep $P = 3$ best *GA* and look for similar shapes using Euclidean distance in PCA space. We decided to keep several cluster representatives to reduce the influence of atlas ranking errors and to relatively increase the shape variability of the final atlas set. Restricting ourselves to one cluster may increase the risk of failing if the atlas ranking or the shape-based clustering is not accurate. We could use other criteria to include similar shapes in *SA* such as all samples in the P clusters but we decided to use Euclidean distance in PCA space because of the different cluster size (from 1 to 14) and because we aimed to have the same number of atlases for all targets to have comparable computational time for all cases. We also based our decision of having a final set of 15 *SA* on the computational time. Using 3 representatives and 5 related atlases was experimentally found to provide the best compromise between accuracy and computational time but it still needs validation and would probably need to be adjusted depending on the training set (i.e. number of clusters found and samples in each cluster).

Most atlas selection methods require non-rigid registration between the target image and the atlases. To reduce the computational cost of such high number of registrations some methods perform offline atlas to atlas registration in order to cluster similar atlases together. Compared to those methods our shape based atlas ranking reduces the number of non-rigid registrations required.

2.5 Conclusions

In this chapter we have shown that atlas selection is an important step in MAS and we have proposed a two-step strategy to identify the most appropriate set of atlases for segmenting highly variable structures such as the LA. We showed that a simple sampling approach was able to capture LA morphology and could be used to automatically group together similar shapes. Shape information could be therefore used to discard bad atlases prior to registration avoiding a high number of computationally expensive registrations and improving segmentation results.

**Fast quasi-conformal regional
flattening of the left atrium**

Abstract – Two-dimensional representation of 3D anatomical structures is a simple and intuitive way for analysing patient information across populations and image modalities. It also allows convenient visualizations that can be included in clinical reports for a fast overview of the whole structure. While cardiac ventricles, especially the left ventricle, have an established standard representation (e.g. bull’s eye plot), the 2D depiction of the left atrium (LA) is challenging due to its sub-structural complexity including the pulmonary veins (PV) and the left atrial appendage (LAA). Quasi-conformal flattening techniques, successfully applied to cardiac ventricles, require additional constraints in the case of the LA to place the PV and LAA in the same geometrical 2D location for different cases. Some registration-based methods have been proposed but 3D (or 2D) surface registration is time-consuming and prone to errors if the geometries are very different. We propose a novel atrial flattening methodology where a quasi-conformal 2D map of the LA is obtained quickly and without errors related to registration. In our approach, the LA is divided into 5 regions which are then mapped to their analogue two-dimensional regions. A dataset of 67 human left atria from magnetic resonance images (MRI) was studied to derive a population-based 2D LA template representing the averaged relative locations of the PVs and LAA. The clinical application of the proposed methodology is illustrated on different use cases including the integration of MRI and electroanatomical data.

This chapter is adapted from: Nuñez-García, M., Bernardino, G., Camara, O., and Butakoff, C. *Fast quasi-conformal regional flattening of the left atrium*, 2018. Under review in *Computerized Medical Imaging and Graphics*.

3.1 Introduction

Medical imaging techniques are increasingly used nowadays to extract crucial anatomical and functional information used in diagnosis and treatment planing. The imaged organs are inherently three-dimensional and appropriate visualization tools are needed, including manual rotations and different points of view, to get a complete overview of the whole organ under study.

Flattening methods aim to compute an unfolded representation of a 3D surface mesh by projecting it to a simpler 2D domain, easier to visualize, manage and interpret. Additionally, if the 2D map is standardised (e.g. same anatomical regions of different subjects spatially coincide) the 2D unfolded domains can be used as a common reference space to analyse multi-modal data from different patients or from the same patient at different time-steps. The reader is referred to [Kreiser et al. \(2018\)](#) for a thorough review of flattening methods applied to human organs, including the brain, different bones, and the vascular system among others.

In the case of the heart, the 17 segment AHA bull’s eye plot of the left ventricle (LV) has been widely used by clinicians for long time ([Cerqueira et al., 2002](#); [Paun et al., 2017](#); [Soto-Iglesias et al., 2016](#)). The LV’s conical shape and the absence of salient sub-structures in 3D anatomies derived from medical images (e.g. ignoring the trabeculations) highly facilitates its flattening. In general, only one basal boundary is considered, which is mapped to the outer contour of a 2D disk, and one reference point (the apex) which is placed in the centre of the circle. On the contrary, unfolding of the LA is challenging since its main cavity is connected to several pulmonary veins, the left atrial appendage and the left ventricle through the mitral valve (MV). Furthermore, there exists a notable variability in the anatomical configuration and spatial location of these sub-structures. For instance, the most common LA morphology (up to 70%) involves 4 PV (with variable size, shape, position and orientation with respect to the main cavity) with occasional presence of a common left trunk, extra right PV or other oddities ([Prasanna et al., 2014](#)). Strong variation can also be seen in the LAA shape and the MV size, shape and position with respect to the PVs ([García-Isla et al., 2018](#)). Proposing a common reference space for the LA, including the multiple possible interfaces between the main cavity and its sub-structures, is therefore non trivial.

[Ma et al. \(2012\)](#) were the first researchers proposing a LA flattening technique, based on a B-spline with proportional distance between any pair of

points in the 3D LA surface and their mapped pairs on the 2D map. As a result, the different 2D maps were not standardised since the position of the PV holes were not in the same position for different patients. Karim et al. (2014) proposed to flatten the LA to a square also without constraining the position of the PV and LAA holes. The authors carefully studied the distortion induced by the unfolding process and showed how the LA flattened square could be used to display and qualitatively analyse different types of data from the same patient. However, a direct comparison across different patients was not feasible because of the lack of correspondence between the different maps (e.g. PV holes were not positioned in the same place). More recently, Williams et al. (2017) proposed a standardised unfold map (SUM) suitable to compare different LA using as reference a 3D LA template and its corresponding 2D flattened version, both related with a defined 3D-2D point-to-point mapping. Their flattening strategy was based on registering an arbitrary LA to the 3D template and then transferring the data to the 2D LA template with the known 3D-2D template mapping. The original LA template was divided into 24 regions, allowing regional analysis of the mapped data. The main limitation of this approach is the difficulty of obtaining an accurate registration between different LA surface meshes due to their high shape variability. Together with errors induced by required data projection and interpolation steps, this scheme leads to undesired information loss between the 3D and 2D LA representations if the LA under study is substantially different from the LA template. Additionally, advanced surface mesh registration techniques such as currents-based ones are associated to large computational times.

In this work, we propose a quasi-conformal (in general, there is no conformal map compatible with a given map along the boundary) flattening of the LA with the following boundary constraints: the MV contour is mapped to the external circumference of a 2D disk, and the PVs and LAA ostia contours are mapped to predefined circumferences within the disk. Quasi-conformal flattening of surface meshes with holes often results in undesired mesh self-folding (holes appear covered by adjacent mesh cells) and to overcome this issue, we impose additional regional constraints. Five anatomical regions are defined in the 3D LA which are afterwards confined to their 2D counterparts. Our method is fast (almost real-time) and without information loss (all points in the 3D mesh are represented in the 2D domain). In order to define a realistic two-dimensional template, the relative position of the PVs and LAA as well as the different PV and LAA ostium sizes need to be considered. We computed the average position of these sub-structures

analysing a population of 67 atrial shapes and used them to define an intuitive and realistic unfolded representation of the LA, that at the same time minimizes the distortion inherent to any flattening technique. To illustrate the proposed methodology we used several synthetic datasets, real LA from Late-Gadolinium Enhanced Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (LGE-CMR) data and real electroanatomical maps.

3.2 Methods

A scheme of the complete flattening framework can be seen in Figure 3.1 and it is described in section 3.2.1. The methodology employed to define the most appropriate 2D template is detailed in section 3.2.2.

3.2.1 Flattening pipeline

The method comprises three main steps: (1) LA cavity extraction; (2) boundary and regional constraints definition; and (3) Fast Regional Flattening (FRF).

3.2.1.1 LA cavity extraction

Given any arbitrary 3D surface mesh representing a LA, the first step aims at standardising the LA shape by only keeping its main cavity after semi-automatically cutting the PVs, the LAA and the MV. This cutting process requires to manually place 5 seeds near the ending points of the PVs and the LAA. The reader is referred to [Tobon-Gomez et al. \(2015\)](#) for more details on this method.

3.2.1.2 Boundary and regional constraints definition

In the second stage, holes in the main LA cavity corresponding to interfaces with the PV and the LAA are closed and triangulated using the method described in [Liepa \(2003\)](#). Then, 9 seed points are manually placed in specific atrial regions: 5 at the centre of the closed PV and LAA ostia, and other 4 on the MV contour: 2 delimiting the interatrial septal wall and 2 delimiting the left lateral wall. Inter-seed geodesic paths (i.e. shortest

Figure 3.1: Overview of the proposed method: (1) LA cavity extraction; (2) boundary and regional constraints definition (LA division); (3) Fast Regional Flattening (FRF). Six boundaries (displayed in red) corresponding to the MV, 4 PV, and LAA ostia are used. Nine segment paths (s_1 - s_9 , in yellow) are used to define 5 LA regions (R1-R5). Data mapped into the LA surface mesh correspond to intensity values from the associated late-gadolinium magnetic resonance image (blue and red colors indicate low and high image intensity, respectively). LSPV = left superior PV; LIPV = left inferior PV; RSPV = right superior PV; RIPV = right inferior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage; MV = mitral valve; MV_1 , MV_2 = seed points in the MV contour delimiting the septal wall, and MV_3 , MV_4 = seed points in the MV contour delimiting the left lateral wall.

curve between two points on a mesh, such that the curve lies on the surface (Mitchell et al., 1987), s_1 - s_9 in Figure 3.1) are computed dividing the LA surface into 5 anatomical regions (R1-R5 in Figure 3.1):

- R1 defines the inter-atrial septal wall, which is delimited by inter-seed geodesic connecting the 2 right PVs (s_1), geodesics connecting them with the MV septal seeds (s_5 and s_6), and the corresponding piece of MV contour between MV_1 and MV_2 .
- R2 corresponds to the part of the posterior wall and LA floor delimited by the 2 inferior PVs (s_2), the geodesics connecting them with the MV

contour (s_6 and s_7), and the MV contour between MV_2 and MV_3 .

- R3 corresponds to the left lateral wall and it is delimited by the geodesics connecting the MV contour with the LAA (s_9), the LAA with the LSPV (s_8), the two left PVs (s_3), the LIPV with the MV contour (s_7), and the MV contour between MV_3 and MV_4 .
- R4 defines the anterior wall, which is bounded by geodesics connecting the MV contour and the RSPV (s_5), both superior veins (s_4), the LSPV and LAA (s_8), the LAA and MV contour (s_9), and the MV contour between MV_4 and MV_1 .
- R5 corresponds to the part of the posterior wall framed by the geodesics connecting the 4 PVs (s_{1-4}).

After that, the final LA cavity that will be flattened is obtained by automatically removing the PV and LAA hole covers. The *boundary constrained points* are identified as the PV, LAA and MV boundary points (mesh vertices of the red curves in Figure 3.1), and the *regional constrained points* are identified as the projection of the inter-seed paths (s_1 - s_9) onto the final LA cavity (points of the yellow curves in Figure 3.1).

In our framework, the PV and LAA ostium contours are mapped to discretised circumferences and their correct representation depends on the sampling (total number of vertices or points) of the ostia contours: a small number of points induces circumferences with large edges, while a high number of points produces circumferences with very short edges. The LAA and PV ostia contours are actually divided into 2 and 3 sub-contours, respectively, as a consequence of the LA regional division explained above, further influencing how the circumferences are represented in the 2D domain. Initially, these sub-contours are determined by the inter-seeds paths which likely cause non-equidistant point distribution in the contour (Figure 3.2a). An equidistant distribution of points (Figure 3.2b) can be achieved by conveniently displacing the sub-contour point extremes (or intersection points: blue, orange and pink dots in Figure 3.2), but this could potentially worsen the anatomical meaning of the LA division (note the red arrow showing how the red line connecting RSPV and RIPV is twisted), and induce mesh distortion (see areas with stretched triangles (highlighted with semi-transparent red ellipses in Figure 3.2b)). Defining as *proportional length* the number of points of each sub-contour corresponding to an equidistant distribution of points in the complete hole, and *real length*

as the number of points of the sub-contour derived from the initial LA division, a good compromise between suitable distribution of points and meaningful LA division is achieved by imposing a sub-contour length equal to $real\ length + \lfloor (proportional\ length - real\ length)/2 \rfloor$ number of points. Note that the second addend can be either positive or negative. One intersection point is fixed (point with index 0 and blue color in Figure 3.2) and the remaining two are updated using the previous rule. This modifies the number of points in each sub-contour but the total number of points remains the same. Using the updated sub-contour extremes, the *boundary* and *regional constrained points* are recomputed.

Figure 3.2: Constraints recomputation. On the left, 3D LA surface mesh (RSPV detail) with different divisions considered: initial seed-based division (black paths); division achieved imposing equidistant points in the hole (red paths); and our proposed division (yellow paths). Contour points (vertices) are enumerated, and initial sub-contour extremes (intersection points) are shown in blue (fixed reference point), orange and pink. On the right, flattened RSPV ostium contour using the original geodesic paths (a), recomputed paths using equidistant points (b) and recomputed paths using the proposed division (c). The RSPV point seed (green) is slightly displaced to the border of the RSPV ostium to exaggerate this effect in the example. $rspv_i = i$ -th sub-contour of RSPV ostium contour; RSPV = right superior PV.

3.2.1.3 Fast Regional Flattening (FRF)

Overview

We aim to obtain a quasi-conformal (i.e. angle-preserving) and standardised flat representation of the 3D LA cavity surface mesh where the boundaries (MV, PV and LAA holes) are constrained to predefined circumferences within the 2D disk. An example of conformal LA flattening where only the MV boundary position is imposed (i.e. only MV boundary is mapped to the circumference of the 2D disk) can be seen in Figure 3.3a. All holes

Figure 3.3: Example of 3D LA surface mesh (left column, 3 different views) and different LA unfolding strategies: (a) quasi-conformal flattening constraining only the MV to the external boundary of a 2D disk; (b) quasi-conformal flattening additionally fitting the PV and LAA hole contours; (c) quasi-conformal flattening fitting PV, LAA contours and imposing regional constraints; (d) final flattening after boundary refinement of (c) mesh. LSPV = left superior PV; LIPV = left inferior PV; RSPV = right superior PV; RIPV = right inferior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage; MV = mitral valve.

except the MV were closed prior to the flattening and opened afterwards. In order to additionally restrict the PV and LAA ostia contours to predefined positions we add the corresponding boundary constraints to the quasi-conformal scheme. By doing that, the boundary points appear correctly placed in the targeted positions but the holes are often covered by adjacent triangles since the method does not avoid mesh self-folding (Figure 3.3b). To overcome this issue, we include additional regional constraints in the parameterisation, but minor triangle overlapping can still occur near the holes (Figure 3.3c). To further refine the boundary we recompute the point coordinates on the 2D flattened LA with a quasi-conformal parameterisation only constrained with the boundary points and not the regional

constraints (Figure 3.3d).

Mathematical framework

Let M be the LA cavity surface mesh with N vertices (points) and M_F its corresponding flattened mesh. Let $I_{\partial M}$ be the indices of the *boundary points* (MV, PV, LAA) of M . Let Δ_M be the $N \times N$ (cotangent (Pinkall and Polthier, 1993)) Laplacian of M and let Δ'_M be Δ_M where the off-diagonal elements of the rows defined by the positions of $I_{\partial M}$ set to 0 and corresponding elements on the main diagonal set to 1. Let (b_x, b_y) be the coordinates of the 2D *boundary points* of M_F in the same order as the corresponding indices appear in $I_{\partial M}$ and let \mathbf{b}'_x and \mathbf{b}'_y be N -dimensional vectors with values \mathbf{b}_x and \mathbf{b}_y , respectively, in the positions of $I_{\partial M}$ and zeros elsewhere.

Let P be the number of *regional constrained points* (i.e. number of points in the dividing segments (s_1 - s_9), yellow lines in Figure 3.1) and I_s the corresponding point (vertex) indices. Let (s_x, s_y) be the 2D coordinates of the P vertices in the same order as they appear in I_s and let \mathbf{E}_s be a $P \times N$ zero matrix with 1 in each row in the positions corresponding to vertices of I_s (i-th row has 1 in the position given by the i-th element of I_s).

In order to find the coordinates $(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)$ of the vertices of M_F , we propose to solve the following two quadratic programming problems:

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{x}} (w \left\| \Delta'_M \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{b}'_x \right\|^2) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{E}_s \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{s}_x \quad (3.1)$$

$$\mathbf{y}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{y}} (w \left\| \Delta'_M \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{b}'_y \right\|^2) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{E}_s \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{s}_y \quad (3.2)$$

with w (set to 1000 in our experiments) penalizing the unfulfilment of the *boundary constraints*. Using Lagrange multipliers these can be rewritten and solved as a system of linear equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} w^2 \Delta_M'^T \Delta_M' & \mathbf{E}_s^T \\ \mathbf{E}_s & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}^* \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_x \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} w^2 \Delta_M'^T \mathbf{b}'_x \\ \mathbf{s}_x \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} w^2 \Delta_M'^T \Delta_M' & \mathbf{E}_s^T \\ \mathbf{E}_s & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}^* \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} w^2 \Delta_M'^T \mathbf{b}'_y \\ \mathbf{s}_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.4)$$

To refine the boundary we proceed as follows. Let Δ_F be the $N \times N$ Laplacian of M_F and let Δ'_F be Δ_F where the off-diagonal elements of the rows defined by the positions of $I_{\partial M}$ set to 0 and corresponding elements on the main diagonal set to 1. The refined coordinates $(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)$ of the vertices of M_F in the final flat representation can be found by solving the following system of linear equations:

$$\Delta'_F \mathbf{x}^* = \mathbf{b}'_x \quad (3.5)$$

$$\Delta'_F \mathbf{y}^* = \mathbf{b}'_y \quad (3.6)$$

The need for this boundary refinement is illustrated in Figure 3.4 where the initial flattening is depicted in red and the final solution is depicted in green.

Figure 3.4: Zoom of PV holes region after the initial flattening (red) and after boundary refinement (green). Target boundaries are shown in black. LSPV = left superior PV; RIPV = right inferior PV; RSPV right superior PV.

Pseudocode corresponding to the complete flattening procedure is shown in Algorithm 1.

3.2.2 2D template definition

Overview

To define the size and position of the PV and LAA circumferences so that they reflect their physiological relative location as much as possible, we analysed 67 manually segmented LA (image resolution of $0.625 \times 0.625 \times 0.625 \text{ mm}^3$) from the 2018 Atrial Segmentation Challenge³ characterised

³<http://atriaseg2018.cardiacatlas.org/>

Algorithm 1 Complete flattening pipeline

```

1: procedure FLAT(mesh) ▷ triangular mesh
2:   Clip PV, LAA, MV
3:   Cover PV, LAA holes
4:   Divide LA: select and connect 9 seeds.
5:   Remove PV, LAA covers → get M, boundary and regional constrained points. Get intersection points (IP) as boundary ∩ regional constrained points. Get all PV sub-contours: portion of a boundary between 2 consecutive IP. Each PV boundary is made by the concatenation of 3 sub-contours
6:   Recompute constraints:
7:   for each PV boundary do
      1. Compute  $L_{12}, L_{23}, L_{31}$ , real length (i.e. number of points) of each sub-contour
      2. Compute  $P_{12}, P_{23}, P_{31}$ , proportional length of each sub-contour
      3. Fix  $IP_1$ 
      4. Displace  $IP_2$ ,  $\lfloor \frac{P_{12}-L_{12}}{2} \rfloor$  points
      5. Displace  $IP_3$ ,  $\lfloor \frac{P_{23}-L_{23}}{2} \rfloor$  points
8:   end for
9:   Using all new IP, update boundary and regional constrained points
10:  Flatten M by solving eq. (3-4)
11:  Refine the solution by solving eq. (5-6)
12:  return  $M'_F$ 
13: end procedure

```

by 4 separate PVs. The remaining atria from the challenge (33) presented different number of PVs or merged LAA and LSPV due to segmentation errors or imaging limitations. We first homogenised the meshes by clipping the PVs, LAA and MV using the procedure proposed by Tobon-Gomez et al. (2015). We measured the perimeter of PVs and LAA ostia; left and right carina lengths (i.e. distance between ipsilateral (same side) veins (s_1 and s_3 in Figure 3.1)); distance between the 2 inferior and the 2 superior veins, respectively (s_2 and s_4); distance between LSPV and LAA (s_5); and distance between right and left veins and the MV (s_6 - s_9). We also used the 67 shapes to build a mean shape or template (shown in Figure 3.3) using Deformetrica (Routier et al., 2015).

Besides considering a realistic relative position of PVs and LAA, we addi-

tionally aimed to reduce distortion in the disk and achieve intuitive visualization. The small MV contour is mapped to a fairly bigger region, i.e. the contour of the disk, while at the same time constraining the remaining surface to the interior of the disk. This fact naturally induces stretching of the outer part of the disk and shrinkage of the interior (see Figure 3.3a) causing high compression of information in the centre. Because of that, we created two additional templates modifying the measured PV and LAA relative positions to enlarge the central part of the disk and achieve better visualization.

An ideal 3D-2D mapping should transform the mesh elements (i.e. triangles) in an isotropic way and preserving their area. Therefore, to analyse the quality of the different LA unfolded maps, we defined distortion indices based on area preservation and transformation isotropy. To quantify the area preservation we first normalised the size of the 3D and the corresponding 2D LA surfaces to have areas equal to 1. Then, we computed for each triangle the ratio between its area in the 2D disk and in the 3D surface (let α be the ratio). As the total areas were previously normalised, having α bigger than 1 implies triangle enlargement, smaller than 1 implies compression and equal to 1 reflects perfect size preservation. Constant ratio in the whole mesh is desired since it means that all triangles are equally transformed in terms of size. To inspect the isotropy of the transformation we used the Jacobian matrix of the 3D-2D transformation (Lévy et al., 2002):

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} \partial u / \partial x & \partial u / \partial y \\ \partial v / \partial x & \partial v / \partial y \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.7)$$

where (x, y) are point coordinates in the local orthonormal coordinate system of each triangle and (u, v) are the global coordinates of the flat domain. The two eigenvalues of \mathbf{J} characterise the deformation of the triangle with the isotropy estimated as the ratio between the smallest and largest eigenvalue (let β be the ratio, $\beta = 1$ meaning isotropic transformation, and decreasing β meaning anisotropic triangle stretching).

We additionally considered the Spatial Context Preservation (SCP), defined in Kreiser et al. (2018) as a qualitative index that helps the user to contextualize the observed structures: the better the spatial context is preserved, the easier a certain region can be visually related to its corresponding position in the original 3D data. To inspect the SCP of the different templates we created a synthetic texture pattern of same size circles uniformly distributed

on the 3D surface mesh and inspected how the circles were displayed in the different templates.

Template (FRF map) creation

Figure 3.5: Summary of shape measurements. (a) PV and LAA ostium perimeters; (b) ratio between remaining ostium perimeters and LIPV perimeter that is the smallest one and considered as reference; (c) inter PV and LAA distances; (d) ratio of the inter PV and LAA distances and the LSPV-LIPV separation (left carina) which is considered as reference. All distances are reported in mm. LI = left inferior PV; LS = left superior PV; RI = right inferior PV; RS = right superior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage.

Measurements corresponding to the PV and LAA ostium perimeters can be seen in Figure 3.5a and b, and in the Appendix (Table A.1). According to our results the left PVs have significantly smaller perimeter than the right PVs ($p < 10^{-6}$). In particular, perimeters were related as follows: $LIPV <^* LSPV < RIPV <^* RSPV < LAA$ where $<^*$ denotes significantly smaller at the 5% significance level. Taking as a reference the smallest perimeter (LIPV) we established the following perimeter proportional values: $LSPV/LIPV = 1.1$; $RIPV/LIPV = 1.1$; $RSPV/LIPV = 1.35$; and $LAA/LIPV = 1.35$, using population median values (Table A.1, right).

Measurements corresponding to the inter-vein distances (s_{1-4}) and LSPV-LAA distance (s_8) are summarized in Figure 3.5c and d, and in the Appendix (Table A.2). The left carina (i.e. region between the two left veins) was found significantly shorter than the right carina ($p = 0.007$) with median ratio of 1.1. The separation between LSPV and LAA was found significantly higher than the left carina length ($p < 10^{-14}$) with the median proportional ratio of almost 1.6. The separation between the 2 superior and the 2 inferior veins was found comparable ($p = 0.37$) and significantly higher than the carinas ($p < 10^{-80}$). The proportional ratio was estimated as 3.75 approximately (width of the posterior wall with respect to left carina length). Finally, we also found that the distance between left PVs and the MV con-

tour was approximately half of the distance between right PVs and the MV contour.

Once all the ratios were estimated, the remaining step required to define the reference values (i.e. centre and radio of the LIPV circumference, and LIPV-LSPV (left carina) separation). Here the criterion used was to obtain a representation with low and uniform distortion distribution. We considered the SUM proposed by Williams et al. (2017) as the state of the art method and compared it with 3 different template (or FRF map) configurations:

1. *Population-based*: using the proportions measured in the study described above.
2. *Adapted₁*: measured proportions are modified to achieve a more detailed representation of the central part of the disk (i.e. inter-veins region).
3. *Adapted₂*: measured proportions are further modified to achieve SUM-like hole positions.

3.3 Experiments and Results

3.3.1 Distortion analysis of 2D templates

Since the SUM methodology registers any LA to the 3D version of a template and then maps the information to the 2D version of the template, only that mesh (the template) can be fairly compared to our method. Results of flattening the SUM template can be seen in Figure 3.6 where the first row corresponds to the SUM mapping and the other 3 rows to the different FRF maps tested: *Population-based*, *Adapted₁*, and *Adapted₂*. The different columns show, from left to right: the flattened mesh; the spatial distribution of the two distortion metrics (triangle's area ratio, α , and anisotropy of the transformation, β); uniform circles mapping; and histograms of the distortion metrics considered. As it can be seen, SUM showed good triangle size preservation (triangles' area ratio close to 1) but with less compact histogram than the FRF maps where even if the difference between enlarged and compressed regions seemed emphasized (b), the histogram showed that the ratio between the areas was more constant than in the SUM case (most

Figure 3.6: Distortion analysis performed using the 3D SUM template. The first row corresponds to the SUM template, and the other 3 to different FRF maps with different hole positions, *population-based* (second row), *Adapted₁* (third row) and *Adapted₂* (fourth row). (a) displays the mesh cells (triangles), (b) shows the area-related distortion, (c) the anisotropic distortion metric, (d) the result of mapping uniform circles, (e) histogram of 2D/3D areas ratio (α), and (f) histogram of eigenvalues ratio (β).

of the triangles were consistently reduced and only few triangles were enlarged). The SUM mapping had the worst anisotropic distortion profile (less percentage of values close to 1 (f)), especially close to the outer contour of the disk (c). FRF maps showed less anisotropic distortion specially for *Population-based* and *Adapted₁* cases.

With regard to the comparison between the different FRF maps using the SUM template, *Population-based* and *Adapted₁* showed comparable isotropic and area ratio profiles. However, the enlargement of the central part in *Adapted₁* improves the SCP (see Figure 3.6d). *Adapted₂* was worse with regard to all the considered parameters showing higher anisotropic distortion and worse areas ratio resulting in an excessive and artificial vertical stretching of the central part. To decide between the 3 proposed FRF maps, we computed distortion metrics using a cohort of 15 LA. Figure 3.7a

Figure 3.7: Distortion metrics in 15 LA. Distortion metrics do not significantly change depending on the templates.

shows boxplots of the anisotropic distortion metric corresponding to the 15 cases together and, as it can be seen, the three configurations showed comparable results. To determine the template with most compact triangle’s size change, we compared the entropy of each histogram. Lower entropy indicates more stable triangle size change which is preferred in this context. As can be seen in Figure 3.7b, the distortion is again comparable among the 3 configurations. We chose *Adapted*₁ as the best compromise between isotropic transformation, triangle’s area consistency and visual interpretability.

The regional relation between the final FRF map chosen (*Adapted*₁) and the SUM was also studied, and it can be seen in Figure 3.8a how the same regions are placed in different areas in the two 2D disks. We also used synthetic texture patterns to inspect the nature of the deformations induced by the FRF and compare it to the SUM mapping. Figure 3.8b shows a striped pattern representing isocontours of the distance to a point placed in the centre of the region between the 4 veins. Figure 3.8c shows results of mapping a spotted pattern. As it can be seen, circles placed close to the MV appear highly distorted (stretched) in the SUM (e.g. spots number 1, 2, 6 or 8) while the effect of the regional flattening can be observed in the FRF map: note the orientation change of the spots in the region encircled in red, and the different size and shape of spots 8 and 9 (that should be similar since they are close to each other) because they belong to regions R4 and R1, respectively. Importantly, SUM is affected by interpolation errors due to information mapping (in this case, color of the spot) from the 3D LA to the SUM template (note the resolution loss as the circles appear blurred, e.g. in the region encircled in red, and the background color change). On the contrary, using the FRF method, there is no information loss or interpolation errors since all the points in the 3D mesh are represented in the 2D map. Additional synthetic examples can be seen in the Appendix (Figure

B.1).

Figure 3.8: Flattening examples of 3D LA with different synthetic texture patterns on the surface. From top to bottom: 4 views of a sample LA divided into the 5 anatomical regions considered in our approach and regional correspondence to SUM and FRF maps (a); striped synthetic texture, defined on the 3D surface representing isocontours of the distance to a seed point placed in the posterior wall (b); and synthetic texture of 100 uniformly distributed spots (c). Some spots have been numbered in the different representations for clarification purposes.

3.4 Clinical applications

Several examples of FRF applied to the visualization of LGE-CMR image intensities are shown in the Appendix (Figure B.2). Besides the usefulness of the method for visualization purposes, in the following subsections, we present two clinical applications: quantification of incomplete ablation lines (gaps) after pulmonary vein isolation (PVI) and joint analysis of bipolar voltage information from electroanatomical maps (EAM) and LGE-MRI intensity data.

Figure 3.9: Examples of clinical applications of FRF. 1. Gap quantification using the FRF method: from left to right: sub-regions are defined in a high resolution FRF map template as the surrounding of each PV (top row) or the surroundings of the two ipsilateral (same-side) PVs (bottom row); the defined subdivision is transferred to the FRF map obtained from an arbitrary LA (b) and then to the corresponding 3D arbitrary LA (c); automatic detection and quantification of gaps (in red) is performed on the 3D LA (d) and optionally displayed on the disk (e). 2. Two examples of electroanatomical maps (EAM) and corresponding (same patient) LA from LGE-CMR with projected image intensity. Low voltage (dark blue) is typically associated to high LGE-CMR intensity (red). LGE-CMR = Late Gadolinium Enhanced Cardiac Magnetic Resonance.

3.4.1 Gap quantification.

PVI is a common procedure for the treatment of AF that aims to electrically isolate the PVs from the LA body producing (with radiofrequency, laser or cryoballoon) a continuous lesion completely encircling the PVs. The resulting lesion is often incomplete being a combination of scar and gaps of healthy tissue that are potential causes for AF recurrence. We have previously developed a semi-automatic method to locate and quantify ablation gaps (Nuñez-García et al., 2018) once a parcellation of the LA is available. Different parcellations can be defined in our FRF map and used to con-

sistently divide different 3D LA in order to apply the gap quantification method. An example of the procedure can be seen in Figure 3.9-1. To identify gaps after PVI, the surroundings of the different PVs independently (Figure 3.9-1, top row) or in pairs (Figure 3.9-1 bottom row) must be inspected. The regions where the gaps are sought for were first defined in a high resolution FRF map used as template and were then transferred to the arbitrary FRF map using a closest point mapping and to the 3D LA using the mesh point identifier. After that, the automatic detection and quantification of the gaps was performed as described in Nuñez-Garcia et al. (2018).

3.4.2 Inspection of the relation between EAM and LGE-CMR data

The proposed FRF maps can also be used to inspect multi-modal data from the same patient. The relation between voltage in EAM and signal intensity in LGE-CMR data has been investigated providing contradictory results (Bisbal et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2015a; Spragg et al., 2012). Figure 3.9-2 shows two examples of EAM invasively acquired during an electrophysiology study (using CARTO (Biosense Webster Inc, Diamond Bar, CA) mapping system) and corresponding (i.e. same patient) LA segmented from LGE-CMR with image intensity projected onto the surface. More examples are shown in the Appendix (Figure B.3). It can be seen how FRF puts into correspondence the two different (due to the different acquisition methods) LA anatomies facilitating their qualitative and quantitative comparison.

3.5 Discussion

We have proposed a novel, fast and information lossless LA flattening framework that could be also applied to other similar structures (e.g. the right atria) only requiring the adaptation of the template (*boudary* and *regional constraints*) to the specific structure’s anatomy.

We thoroughly compared our method to the SUM mapping, the state of the art method for atrial standardised representation. Contrary to the SUM method, FRF does not depend on registration being therefore faster and not affected by potential registration errors. Additionally, FRF does not lose any information from the initial 3D surface, i.e. all points are depicted

in the 2D map, while SUM needs to interpolate data when mapping the information from the arbitrary 3D surface to the template. This is especially noticeable in the flattening of the spotted patterns (color represents spot identifier) where the texture appears blurred after the flattening process (Figure 3.6c). This effect is even more noticeable in the example in Appendix (Figure B.1c) where it can be seen how many spots have merged due to resolution loss. These errors could be reduced by remeshing the SUM template (increasing the number of points) but this will increase the registration computational cost. The execution time of the registration using the original SUM template (mesh with 7402 points) is around 20 minutes (Nuñez-García et al., 2018) while FRF lasts 2-3 s, after manual seed points placement (Intel i5 3.3 GHz CPU and 16 GB RAM).

The distortion induced by the two methods is different as showed in Figure 3.6. SUM method performs a global mapping where the central part is enlarged and the areas close to the MV are pushed and stretched along the contour of the disk. On the other hand, FRF restricts each area to its specific 2D domain (enhancing regional interpretability) even if this fact causes local stretching/shrinkage and distortion close to the limits of the 5 defined regions.

SUM provides more detailed regional division (24 regions (Williams et al., 2017) vs. our 5 regions) but this regional division may be inaccurate due to the small size of some regions and the influence of registration errors. FRF brings more control on the 3D regional division by manual placement of seed points and, in the flattening, constraining each region to its specific 2D area. Our algorithm is however highly influenced by this manual seed placement step, especially regarding the seeds placed on the MV contour. The seed points and inter-seed paths define the constraints used in the flattening which is the key part of the method. Automatically computing the constraints, i.e. automatically dividing the LA is challenging due to, for example, bulges in the LA and obliqueness of the MV plane. Nonetheless, since the process of seed placement and unfolding is almost real time it can be repeated several times until a satisfactory result is obtained. Additionally, more regions could be defined in our FRF template to further subdivide any arbitrary LA as in Figure 3.9-1 a-c.

Side-by-side or overlaying inspection of different FRF maps is convenient in many clinical situations: to analyse the temporal evolution of some parameter (e.g. pre- and post-ablation fibrosis extent) from the same patient; to compare and correlate different features from the same patient (e.g. gadolin-

ium enhancement from LGE-CMR data and endocardial voltage from electroanatomical maps); to compare same feature in different patients (e.g. regional or global fibrosis extent (Benito et al., 2018)), etc. We have shown pairwise comparisons of LGE-CMR intensities and bipolar endocardial voltage but a better depiction of the electroanatomical maps is required (e.g. using high definition mapping systems like Rhythmia (HDx Mapping System, Boston Scientific)) to achieve realistic representations of the LA and be able to fairly compare it with other kinds of data such as LGE-MRI.

Proposing a standard 2D template is far from trivial. We observed how depending on the specific 3D atrial shape, different configurations (mainly radius and position of the holes) were preferable. We developed a template that can be used for most of the LA shapes (with 4 veins), which takes into account the real averaged inter-vein (and LAA) separation and facilitates visualization and interpretability of the 2D map. However, the estimated metrics (proportions) were obtained using a dataset of AF patients, i.e. bigger, more spherical LA and with bigger PV ostia than controls. Woźniak-Skowerska et al. (2011) showed how diameters of PV ostia were larger in AF patients than in control subjects in accordance with increased LA volume of the AF patients. Additionally, Lickfett et al. (2005) found that the PV orifice size depended on the cardiac cycle with the largest diameter in late atrial systole with a mean reduction of 32.5% in atrial systole. Nonetheless, we believe that the changes in the size of the atrium or ostia will not change significantly our distortion analysis.

The method presents some limitations. First, it can only be applied to LA with 4 PVs. Other templates can be derived similarly to the one proposed here but direct comparison with the 4-veins template will not be accurate in regions close to the PV holes. The method can be applied to atria with a common left trunk if there exist a distant bifurcation but it should be taken into account that the region represented between the veins would not be the carina but the common left trunk itself. LA with extra veins (e.g. extra middle right PV) can also be flattened with our method if the vein can be clipped or ignored. This solution may be acceptable depending on the application. For example, it could be done to quantify global extent of fibrosis but it should be avoided if the representation of the surroundings of the PVs is important, for example in gap detection after pulmonary vein isolation. Our method may provide unsatisfactory results in the case of low resolution meshes (few points) and with PVs very close to each other. In that case, the number of points between the veins may not be sufficient to depict the template and the triangles may appear stretched.

The code (Python) will be publicly available once the corresponding paper is published.

3.6 Conclusion

We have presented a method to unfold any 3D LA surface and depict it in an intuitive, standardised, two-dimensional map. Compared to the SUM it does not rely on a registration step, much faster and guarantees no information loss, as it could happen due to a bad registration or information interpolation when the source and target meshes have very different shapes and resolutions. Moreover, it emphasizes regional interpretability by confining anatomical regions to predefined regions in the 2D map avoiding undesired displacements attributable to global flattening methods. We have shown the suitability of our method to easily inspect the whole LA anatomy in 1 view, and to consistently divide the different LA anatomies and put them into correspondence making its regional comparison possible.

Appendix. Shape metrics.

Table A.1: Mean, standard deviation (SD) and median of the PVs and LAA ostium perimeters (left) and perimeter ratio with respect to LIPV which is the smallest one and considered as reference (right). All distances are reported in mm. LIPV = left inferior PV; LSPV = left superior PV; RIPV = right inferior PV; RSPV = right superior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage.

	Perimeter (mm)					Perimeters ratio			
	LIPV	LSPV	RIPV	RSPV	LAA	$\frac{LSPV}{LIPV}$	$\frac{RIPV}{LIPV}$	$\frac{RSPV}{LIPV}$	$\frac{LAA}{LIPV}$
Mean	38.73	43.06	44.49	50.47	54.30	1.17	1.18	1.36	1.48
SD	9.17	7.37	9.91	11.21	14.06	0.35	0.29	0.39	0.50
Median	38.32	41.84	46.11	49.39	52.61	1.14	1.13	1.34	1.39

Table A.2: Mean, standard deviation and median of the inter-veins and LAA distance (left) and distance ratio with respect to the LS-LI (left carina) distance which is considered as reference (right). All distances are reported in mm. LI = left inferior PV; LS = left superior PV; RI = right inferior PV; RS = right superior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage.

	Distance (mm)					Distance ratio			
	LS-LI	RS-RI	RS-LS	RI-LI	LS-LAA	$\frac{RS-RI}{LS-LI}$	$\frac{LS-LAA}{LS-LI}$	$\frac{RS-LS}{LS-LI}$	$\frac{RI-LI}{LS-LI}$
Mean	14.82	17.03	57.66	58.91	23.94	1.18	1.72	4.06	4.15
SD	3.29	5.62	8.61	7.21	7.95	0.36	0.75	1.01	0.99
Median	13.96	15.88	57.98	60.29	22.54	1.09	1.59	3.72	3.81

Appendix. Additional flattening examples.

Figure B.1: Additional flattening examples of 3D LA with different synthetic textures on the surface and corresponding SUM and FRF maps. First and second rows show striped synthetic patterns, defined on the 3D surface representing isocontours of the distance to a seed point placed in the right carina (a), and the MV contour (b). (c) shows a texture of 500 uniformly distributed spots.

Figure B.2: Examples of LA flattening showing 4 views of manually segmented LA surfaces with projected late gadolinium enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (LGE-CMR) intensities and corresponding FRF maps.

Figure B.3: Three examples of EAM and corresponding (same patient) LA from LGE-CMR with projected image intensity. Low voltage (dark blue) is typically associated to high LGE-CMR intensity (red).

Quantification of incomplete ablation lines after pulmonary vein isolation

Abstract – Pulmonary vein isolation (PVI) is a common procedure for the treatment of atrial fibrillation (AF) since the initial trigger for AF frequently originates in the pulmonary veins. A successful isolation produces a continuous lesion (scar) completely encircling the veins that stops activation waves from propagating to the atrial body. Unfortunately, the encircling lesion is often incomplete, becoming a combination of scar and gaps of healthy tissue. These gaps are potential causes of AF recurrence, which requires a redo of the isolation procedure. Late-gadolinium enhanced cardiac magnetic resonance (LGE-CMR) is a non-invasive method that may also be used to detect gaps, but it is currently a time-consuming process, prone to high inter-observer variability. In this chapter, we present a method to semi-automatically identify and quantify ablation gaps. Gap quantification is performed through minimum path search in a graph where every node is a scar patch and the edges are the geodesic distances between patches. We propose the Relative Gap Measure (*RGM*) to estimate the percentage of gap around a vein, which is defined as the ratio of the overall gap length and the total length of the path that encircles the vein. Additionally, an advanced version of the *RGM* has been developed to integrate gap quantification estimates from different scar segmentation techniques into a single figure-of-merit.

This chapter is adapted from:

Nuñez-García, M., Camara, O., O’Neill, M. D., Razavi, R., Chubb, H., and Butakoff, C. (2018). *Mind the gap: quantification of incomplete ablation patterns after pulmonary vein isolation using minimum path search*. *Medical Image Analysis*, 51, 1–12.

4.1 Introduction

Around 33.5 million people suffer from atrial fibrillation (AF) worldwide (Chugh et al., 2013), the most frequent class of arrhythmia. The origin of AF is the appearance of rapid abnormal electrical signals activating the atrium in a disorganized way. Most of these abnormal electrical currents originate inside the pulmonary veins (Haissaguerre et al., 1998). Pulmonary vein isolation (PVI), which aims to electrically isolate the PVs from the main atrial body, is a common treatment, especially for patients not responding to medication. Radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is the most frequent technique for PVI, and it involves the delivery of RF energy with an electrophysiological ablation catheter to create regions of scar tissue that will stop abnormal conduction. Different ablation patterns are possible and their suitability is still under investigation (Bayer et al., 2016). Nonetheless, PVI is considered the cornerstone of the procedure (Calkins et al., 2012), having been proven to terminate AF in many cases (Badger et al., 2010; Verma et al., 2005). However, repeat procedures are frequently required, with the long-term success rate after catheter ablation ranging from 53.1% with a single procedure to almost 80% with multiple procedures (i.e. a redo) (Ganesan et al., 2013).

One of the most frequent reasons for this relatively low success rate is incomplete PVI, caused by the appearance of gaps in the created lesion. In the case of RF ablation, lesion is formed at the tip of the catheter that is placed at discrete locations along the ablation path. Incomplete ablation lesions can appear due to that punctate (i.e. point by point) nature of the ablation, complexity of the atrial anatomy or complications during the procedure. The difficulty to access with a catheter may also lead to loss of contact and to non-transmural lesions (Glover et al., 2018). Additionally, atrial tissue can recover over time and therefore not all the acute lesions turn into chronic lesions. These are potential factors for the presence of gaps after PVI (Kirchhof and Calkins, 2016), increasing AF recurrence rates (Kuck et al., 2016).

Gaps around PVs can be categorized into electrical (conduction) and anatomical (scar or lesion) ones. Conduction gaps are detected with intra-cavitary catheters during a redo procedure, and correspond to sites of electrical reconnection (i.e. high voltage in the electrocardiogram). The regional distribution of conduction gaps in the left atria after PVI was investigated by Godin et al. (2013) and Galand et al. (2016). On the other hand, lesion gaps are related to healthy tissue patches in the (ideally continuous) scar lesion.

The relation between electrical and lesion gaps is still not fully understood; contradictory results can be found in the literature, from high (Bisbal et al., 2014) to low (Harrison et al., 2015a; Spragg et al., 2012) agreement in the location of both types of gaps. This disagreement is partially due to the lack of a consistent and objective way to detect and characterize ablation gaps, mainly relying on visual inspection of the data.

Ablation lesions (and therefore gaps) are typically identified using Late Gadolinium Enhancement Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (LGE-CMR). Gap detection in LGE-CMR remains challenging since there is a lack of consensus with respect to the most appropriate scar segmentation technique. The interested reader is referred to Pontecorboli et al. (2016) for a recent review on scar detection in the atria with LGE-CMR. Most of scar segmentation techniques are semi-automatic and based on image thresholding: voxels are classified as scar or healthy tissue if an intensity-related value is above or below a given threshold, respectively. Many methods use a threshold calculated as a specific number of standard deviations (SD) above a reference value (e.g. mean intensity in the blood pool), but it is not clear which SD value is optimal: Harrison et al. (2014) proposed 3.3 SD after histological validation, while the same research group did not find significant differences using 2, 3 or 4 SD in a previous study (Karim et al., 2013). Recently, Chubb et al. (2018b), studying the reproducibility of LGE-CMR imaging, suggested that the intensity thresholding based on the mean and SD of the blood pool voxel intensity provided the most consistent scar identification between repeated LGE-CMR scans of the same patient. Other threshold-based segmentation techniques are based on the Image Intensity Ratio (IIR), computed as the signal intensity divided by the mean of the blood pool. Different *IIR* values have been proposed: while some authors (Dewire et al., 2014; Khurram et al., 2014) used a threshold of $IIR > 1.61$ to detect dense scar in pre-ablation cases, Benito et al. (2016) recently found an optimal $IIR > 1.32$ to define dense atrial fibrosis in post-ablation patients. A different strategy was taken by Bisbal et al. 2014, which adapted to atrial scar segmentation the standard thresholds currently used for left ventricle scar characterization in LGE-CMR (60 and 40 $\pm 5\%$ of the maximum intensity value to detect core zone, border zone and healthy tissue, respectively).

Once LA scar is detected, lesion gaps around PVs can be analysed. To the best of our knowledge, methods available in the literature are only based on visual inspection of scar segmentation results, providing qualitative and biased estimations of gap characteristics (i.e. number, position). For ex-

Figure 4.1: Pipeline of the proposed method. 1. Acquisition of left atrial (LA) anatomy and tissue information from Magnetic Resonance Angiogram (MRA) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans respectively. A multi-threshold (T_i) scar segmentation approach is adopted, resulting in five different scar patterns. 2. Semi-automatic parcellation of the LA (each color represents a different region defined in our atlas) and definition of areas where the exploration of gaps will be performed. 3. Detection and quantification of gaps following a graph-based approach and using the *Relative Gap Measure* (RGM). 4. Combination of multi-threshold RGM outcomes with the normalized area under the curve (RGM_{NAUC}). Shown is the RGM of only one search area (left PVs).

ample, Peters et al. (2007) visually inspected LGE-CMR data to estimate the circumferential completeness and extent of ablation lesions after RF PVI, showing that in their dataset the completeness of the circumference was $88 \pm 11\%$ around the left inferior PV. In Badger et al. (2010) two independent and blinded observers visually identified and quantified scar and lesion gaps in LGE-CMR images concluding that complete circumferential PV scarring of all 4 PVs is difficult to achieve (only 7% of patients after the first procedure) but is related to better clinical outcome. Halbfass et al. (Halbfass et al., 2015) took a similar approach (with three observers) to analyse lesion formation differences after PVI using two types of cryoballoon. The authors concluded that the number of patients with complete circular lesions did not differ significantly in the two groups.

In this chapter we present a consistent, objective and quantifiable definition of PVI gaps that is observer independent, once the scar has been segmented. We construct a graph where nodes are all scar patches around a given PV and edges are the distances between those patches (i.e. length of potential

gaps). We estimate the shortest path in that graph and only the gaps belonging to that path are selected as true gaps. Then, the circumferential extent of the gap is measured as the fraction of the path’s length that corresponds to gap, providing a Relative Gap Measure (*RGM*). A preliminary version of the methodology was published in (Garcia et al., 2015), where gap quantification was performed using a 2D representation of the LA (Williams et al., 2017), so-called Standardised Unfold Map (SUM), which is obtained after flattening a 3D LA template with a pre-defined regional parcellation. Nevertheless, the obtained results were influenced by errors due to the metric distortion caused by the 3D-2D flattening. In this work, we propose an advanced version of our gap quantification method where all the steps have been considerably improved and with the following contributions: a more accurate distance calculation is provided since all measurements are performed directly on the 3D atrial mesh, allowing for an accurate visualization of the detected gaps on the atrial surface that could be used to guide a redo procedure; the development of an index representing the percentage of gap around a PV that can combine multiple segmentation results to compensate for the dependence of the process on scar segmentation accuracy; a detailed regional analysis of the gaps is additionally provided; and new PVI scenarios are considered as the typical ablation approach consisting in jointly isolating the two ipsilateral (i.e. same side) veins. The method is highly reproducible only requiring minimal user interaction at the left atrial mesh processing step. To verify the proposed algorithm we generated a fully-controlled synthetic dataset of typical scar patterns around PVs.

4.2 Methods

The main steps of the algorithm are shown in Figure 4.1 and explained in the following subsections. Briefly, once a left atrial geometry has been segmented from imaging data, several scar segmentations are obtained by applying different thresholds (T_i) to image intensities (Step 1). Note that the thresholding in this step can be replaced by any scar segmentation algorithm. In parallel, a semi-automatic parcellation of the LA is obtained to define gap search areas (Step 2). Subsequently, a graph is built for every scar segmentation result, where the nodes and edges correspond to scar patches and distances between them, respectively (Step 3). The graph is then analysed to quantify the amount of scar gap around each vein (or pair of veins), which is characterised by the *Relative Gap Measure (RGM)*. Finally,

RGM values from the different T_i threshold segmentations are combined into a single figure-of-merit (RGM_{NAUC}) (Step 4).

The proposed method can be simplified if an accurate scar pattern is available: for each search area, only one graph would be processed resulting in a single RGM value.

Patient data description

Fifty patients undergoing first time ablation for atrial fibrillation between January 2014 and January 2016 at St Thomas' Hospital (London, UK) were included in this study. All of them provided written and informed consent and the study was approved by the National Research Ethics Service (South London Research Ethics Committee reference 08/H0802/68). For patients with a diagnosis of paroxysmal AF and in sinus rhythm, a point-by-point wide area circumferential ablation (WACA) achieving PVI was performed using 8Fr irrigated SmartTouch catheter (Biosense Webster), or 8Fr irrigated TactiCath catheter (St Jude). Target ablation parameters were $>5g$ for at least 15 seconds per RF delivery location. Power was 30W throughout except on the posterior wall, where it was limited to 25W. For patients presenting with persistent AF, a WACA was performed followed by additional ablation lesion sets (mitral line, roof line, inferior posterior line, complex fractionated electrogram ablation) as a step-wise ablation.

CMR imaging was performed on a 1.5 T MR-scanner (Ingenia, Philips Healthcare, Best, Netherlands) three months after the ablation. 3D inversion recovery spoiled gradient echo acquisition was performed with coverage to include the whole LA in axial orientation, using the following MR acquisition parameters: TR 5.5 ms, TE 3.0 ms, flip angle 25° , low-high k-space ordering, respiratory and ECG-triggering (end atrial diastole, maximum 120 ms acquisition window), $1.3 \times 1.3 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ (typically 50 slices per acquisition), SPIR fat suppression. Gadolinium-Based Contrast Agents (GBCA) dose was 0.2 ml/kg Gadovist (Bayer HealthCare Pharmaceuticals, Berlin, Germany). Acquisitions were commenced 30 min post gadolinium-based contrast agent administration (Chubb et al., 2018a). A gated magnetic resonance angiogram (GMRA) 3D dataset was also acquired as a high contrast template. The acquisition was commenced 90 seconds after the start of a slow infusion of GBCA at 0.3ml/second (Groarke et al., 2014) with the same coverage and parameters (previously mentioned) as the subsequent LGE acquisitions.

4.2.1 Left atrial segmentation and tissue characterisation

Left atrial geometries were obtained from the GMRA images with a standard region-growing segmentation technique initialized by manually placed seeds, available in the Open-Source ITK-SNAP⁴ software (Yushkevich et al., 2006). The resulting LA segmentation was then rigidly registered (3 translations and 3 rotations, (Denton et al., 1999)) to the LGE-CMR images and a triangular mesh was built using the classical marching cubes algorithm. Voxel intensities from LGE-CMR images were mapped onto the obtained LA surface mesh using the maximum intensity projection (MIP) technique: images were sampled along the normals on both sides of the surface mesh, assigning the maximum intensity value to the corresponding vertex on the LA mesh. The depth of the sampling was set to 3 mm (0.2 mm between samples). This value is considered to be large enough to overcome potential segmentation errors while at the same time sufficiently small to avoid going too far from the atrial wall (Harrison et al., 2015b; Knowles et al., 2010).

Scar tissue was extracted from LGE-CMR images using intensity thresholding based on the SD of the blood pool intensity since it was the approach that demonstrated better reproducibility (Chubb et al., 2018b). In order to reduce the influence of the SD choice on gap quantification, we identified scar with five different thresholds: 2, 3.3, 4, 5, and 6 SD above the mean intensity of the blood pool. These thresholds were chosen based on the work of Harrison et al. (2014), where the authors obtained the best segmentation accuracy with the 3.3 SD value. According to their results, a non-linear behavior between scar patterns and the choice of SD parameter was observed: SD values lower than the optimal one overestimated the scar in a higher proportion than higher values underestimated it. For this reason, three different SDs were chosen above 3.3 SD and just one below it. In consequence, for each subject we obtained five different scar patterns that were separately processed in the gap detection step. Figure 4.1 (top row) shows the scar patterns obtained by different thresholds in an exemplar case, where scar patches split or disappear (i.e. new gaps appear or merge, respectively) with larger thresholds ($T_1 < T_2 < T_3 < T_4 < T_5$).

⁴www.itksnap.org

Figure 4.2: Different gap search areas depending on the pulmonary vein isolation strategy, illustrated by different colors on 3D LA surface (top) and 2D SUM (bottom) representations. From left to right: *independent-encirclement* with small (a) and large (b) regions; *joint-encirclement* with small (c) and large (d) regions.

4.2.2 Semi-automatic parcellation of the LA

A standardised parcellation of the segmented LA surface is necessary to define the areas where gaps will be searched and to have a common reference system for population-based analysis. We used a parcellation created on a template left atrium (atlas mesh), as we proposed in Williams et al. (2017). An extra separation between left and right parts of the LA was added, leading to 28 regions. This was required to test additional ablation patterns commonly used in clinical routine (see Step 2 in Figure 4.1).

Surface mesh pre-processing

To transfer the defined parcellation in the atlas mesh to any arbitrary LA surface mesh several pre-processing steps were required. The first step aimed at standardising the LA shape by only keeping its main cavity after semi-automatically cutting connected sub-structures such as the PVs, the left atrial appendage (LAA) and the mitral valve. This cutting process only requires to manually place 5 seeds near the ending points of the PVs and the LAA. The reader is referred to Tobon-Gomez et al. (2015) for more details on this method. Once atrial meshes were standardised they were registered to the atlas mesh. The registration stage was composed of an affine transformation followed by a non-rigid registration based on currents (Durrleman et al., 2014). Region labels of the atlas were then transferred to the co-registered segmented LA mesh with a closest-point mapping. Afterwards, region labels were also brought to the original (non-registered) LA mesh, where the subsequent analysis was performed. Additionally, we used

the 2D SUM representation (Williams et al., 2017) of the LA template for visualization purposes.

Gap search areas

Figure 4.3: (a) Example of synthetic data with a patchy scar that suggests many potential gaps. (b) According to our definition, not all of them are true gaps, only the ones shown in red. (c) The complete *Encircling Path* is the concatenation of gaps and paths connecting the gaps across scar patches (red and green paths, respectively).

Figure 4.4: Example of gap detection. (a) Detail of the search area around a PV showing all scar patches in different colors. The artificial scar patches (green and black) created along the cut are also shown, as well as the detected gaps (red) and the rest of the *Encircling Path* (green). The constructed graph (b) and the adjacency matrix (c) are used to determine the shortest path around the PV (colored in red) going from the starting to the ending point. Distances are reported in mm.

The next step of the pipeline defines the areas where gaps will be searched. These areas are related to the chosen PVI strategy. In this work we considered the two most common PVI scenarios in clinical routine:

4.2. METHODS

Figure 4.5: Several distance maps corresponding to an exemplar case (leftmost column). The first row shows the *independent-encirclement* approach and the second row the *joint-encirclement* approach. Each column displays a distance map corresponding to a different scar patch (numbers are patch identifiers) whose contour is also shown in white. The leftmost and rightmost distance maps correspond to the distance transforms of the cutting line (i.e. artificial scar patches). Note the effect of the extra cut needed in the *joint-encirclement* approach to avoid that the *Encircling Path* surrounds only one PV. LSPV = Left Superior PV; LIPV = Left Inferior PV; RIPV = Right Inferior PV; RSPV = Right Superior PV; LAA = Left Atrial Appendage.

- *Independent-encirclement*: The four PVs are independently isolated by creating PV-specific continuous lesions that completely surround each of them;
- *Joint-encirclement*: the two ipsilateral veins (i.e. on the same side, right or left PVs) are jointly isolated by a lesion that simultaneously encircles the two of them.

The two PVI scenarios require a different definition of the gap search area, as illustrated in Figure 4.2. Additionally, different sizes of the search areas were considered: small regions near to the veins or larger regions that would give a more global view. Since oftentimes ablation lines tend to deviate far from PV ostia (e.g. due to undesired catheter movement), we chose to perform the subsequent gap analysis only in the largest search areas (Figure 4.2 (b) and (d)).

4.2.3 Graph-based gap identification and quantification

The developed method is based on our definition of a potential gap as the shortest geodesic distance (i.e. length of the shortest curve between two points on a mesh, such that the curve lies on the surface (Mitchell et al., 1987)) between two disjoint scar patches within a search area. Many paths exist that surround a PV; we define the *Encircling Path* as the closed path that encircles a PV (or two same-side PV together) with the minimum amount of gap, as can be seen in Figure 4.3. In that way, only potential gaps (i.e healthy tissue between scar patches) belonging to the *Encircling Path* are classified as true gaps. Figure 4.3 shows how the proposed method is able to consistently identify the true gaps in a situation where the visual detection and quantification of gaps would be challenging.

We defined a quantitative index to represent the amount of gap in each of the search areas, so-called *Relative Gap Measure (RGM)*, which is obtained as follows:

$$RGM = \frac{Gap\ length}{Encircling\ Path\ length},$$

where *Gap length* (GL) adds up all gap lengths along the *Encircling Path*; and the *Encircling Path length* corresponds to the length of the complete closed loop. The *RGM* ranges from 0 to 1 indicating that the vein is completely encircled if $RGM = 0$ and that there is no scar around the vein if $RGM = 1$.

To find the *Encircling Path* and compute the *RGM*, a graph was built (see Figure 4.4 (b)) where each node was a scar patch and edges were the minimum geodesic distances between pairs of scar patches (i.e. minimum inter-patch distance), that is, the length of the potential gaps. The graph was complete, in the sense that every pair of nodes were connected. The edges of the graph were estimated using the distance transform (Danielsson, 1980; Fabbri et al., 2008) that is computed considering each scar patch separately: it assigns to every point in the mesh a value indicating its distance to the nearest point in the scar patch under study (see Figure 4.5). The two points corresponding to the extremes of the selected path (i.e. associated to the minimum inter patch distance) were identified as gap limits.

Using the graph and its associated adjacency matrix (Figure 4.4 (b) and (c) respectively) we can determine the *Encircling Path*, but with the following

considerations: the starting and ending points in the path must coincide to obtain a closed path; and an orientation must be imposed in the calculation of the path to guarantee that the path completely surrounds the vein. We fulfilled these requirements opening the mesh, by introducing a cutting line coinciding with the atrial region boundaries defined on the LA template. This cutting line was implemented by disconnecting its cells after adding duplicate points: points with the same coordinates but different connectivity. The *Encircling Path* cannot cross the cutting line since duplicate points are disconnected, becoming the extremes of the path. We then introduced two artificial scar patches (and corresponding nodes in the graph) at the cutting line (one to each side) defining the first and the last nodes in our graph. These nodes are the only ones not directly connected in the built graph (see Figure 4.4 (a) and (b)). The detection of the *Encircling Path* is then based on finding the minimum distance between the two extreme nodes using the corresponding adjacency matrix (Figure 4.4 (c)).

Figure 4.6: Examples of *Relative Gap Measure (RGM)* estimations on synthetic data where scar was added around the left inferior PV. In each example the scar pattern is shown, together with the *Encircling Path*, which has two parts: gaps (red) and non-gap paths (green). (a) Examples with scar patterns distant from the PV ostia, illustrating why it is appropriate to compute the *Encircling path* as a concatenation of gaps and geodesics connecting the gaps, i.e. using gap extremes (correct *RGM* result), independently of scar shape (incorrect *RGM* result). (b) Examples of scar patterns with increasing *RGM*. The black contours correspond to an initial scar patch fully encircling the PV at a certain distance from the extreme of the PV. Then, in each example, a percentage of this patch is marked as gap (from left to right: 0%, 25%, 50%, and 75%, respectively).

The first row in Figure 4.5 displays several distance maps where the effect of the cut is shown as a sudden color change in the cutting line. In the *joint-encirclement* approach (second row in Figure 4.5) an additional cut along the line connecting the two involved veins had to be added to prevent the *Encircling Path* surrounding only one vein. This cut was computed using the seeds manually placed in the veins during the surface mesh pre-processing step.

The distances between artificial and real scar patches needed a particular approach to avoid a non-closed *Encircling Path*. Naturally, all points of the cutting line are candidates as starting/ending points of the *Encircling Path*. We built a graph for each possible pair of starting/ending points and selected the ones with the smallest gap length. The shortest path between all possible starting/ending point candidates, was obtained applying the Dijkstra algorithm (Dijkstra, 1959). As a direct output of the algorithm we also obtained the number of gaps (and their lengths) in each *Encircling Path*.

Estimation of the *RGM* index also requires computing the length of the non-gap section in the *Encircling Path*. Scar tissue can present any type of morphology around each PV, but in order to compute the percentage of encirclement completeness, scar morphology is not relevant, and only the corresponding proportion of the PV boundary that is isolated matters. One possibility would be to estimate the geodesics following the scar shape, but this approach would underestimate the *RGM*. Figure 4.6 (a) shows a synthetic example where the gap covers about half of the PV and the scar is quite distant from the PV. If the non-gap part of the *Encircling path* would be estimated following the scar shape, as its length is quite large, the obtained *RGM* would be 0.29, which does not correspond to the correct proportion of gap around the vein. We solved this issue by computing the non-gap part of the *Encircling path* as the geodesics between the two points in the same scar patch identified as gap extremes. The *Encircling path* is then a concatenation of gaps and geodesics connecting consecutive gaps. In the same example, with our approach the *RGM* is 0.46, which is a more reasonable value according to our perception. Similarly, on the right example in Figure 4.6 (a), the *RGM* considering the real shape of the scar would be equal to 0.13 suggesting again a smaller gap.

Besides estimating the *RGM*, the graph-based gap step also provides additional measures to quantify gaps for each PV and pair of veins such as the (accumulated and regional) number and length of gaps. Figure 4.7 shows these gap quantification measures in an exemplar clinical case.

4.2.4 Multi-threshold result integration

As mentioned in Section 4.2.1, we used a multi-threshold protocol for scar segmentation, generating five different scar patterns per case. The proposed

gap quantification pipeline was applied to each segmented scar separately and the results were then integrated as follows.

RGM measurements were combined computing the normalised area under the curve (NAUC) of the plot relating the *RGM* and threshold values (let us denote this measure by RGM_{NAUC}), as can be seen in Figure 4.8. The AUC of the *RGM*-derived curve was estimated using the trapezoidal rule that was then normalized by the maximum area; given that $RGM \in [0, 1]$, it was simply the threshold's range ($T_5 - T_1$). Let $f : T \in [T_1, T_5] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be the function defined on the interval of thresholds assigning the *RGM* value to each threshold. Then, RGM_{NAUC} is obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} RGM_{AUC} &= \int_{T_1}^{T_5} f(T) dT \approx \\ &\approx \sum_{k=1}^4 \frac{f(T_{k+1}) + f(T_k)}{2} (T_{k+1} - T_k), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$RGM_{NAUC} = \frac{RGM_{AUC}}{T_5 - T_1}$$

Besides the RGM_{NAUC} index, the multi-segmentation approach provides statistics (mean and standard deviation) on gap quantification measurements (number and length of gaps) across the different segmentations in each search area.

4.3 Experiments and Results

The performance of the proposed gap detection and quantification methodology was verified on synthetically generated data with varying scar patterns on the LA template mesh. Figure 4.6 (b) shows several synthetic scar patterns where a scar fully encircling the PV was synthetically generated at a distance between 2 and 4 mm from the PV ostium (this region is marked as a black contour in the figure). We then removed 0%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% of the synthetic scar, consequently generating gaps of different size. The results of our gap quantification method were $RGM = 0.00, 0.30, 0.60, 0.77$ and 1.00 , respectively (the last case is not shown in the figure). *RGM* estimations slightly differ from the percentage of scar removed (maximum

Figure 4.7: Example of gap quantification in clinical data with the two studied pulmonary vein isolation strategies: *independent-* and *joint-encirclement* in the first and second rows, respectively. Several views of the atria are shown as well as the corresponding SUM (right). The gaps detected in the different search areas (i.e. RSPV, RIPV, LIPV, LSPV, right PVs and left PVs) are shown with different colors. Notice that some of the gaps are part of the encircling path of the two veins in the same side. In that situation, two parallel gap paths are shown but there is only one gap path (the shortest one) which is the same for both veins.

Figure 4.8: Gap quantification result in a given search area combining multiple scar segmentations. From left to right, an increasing threshold is used which results in an increasing amount of gap and *RGM*. The *Encircling Paths*, composed by gap (red) and non-gap (green) sections, are shown for every scar segmentation. The rightmost figure shows the *RGM* vs threshold curve as well as the *RGM_{NAUC}* value.

deviation of 10%). This is explained by our definition of gap as the smallest portion of healthy tissue around the PV (therefore not following the black contour) and due to the computation of the non-gap section of the *Encircling path* using gap extremes (also not following the black contour which corresponds to the scar patch in this case).

4.4 Discussion

The purpose of the work presented in this chapter was to develop a method to detect and quantify incomplete ablation patterns (gaps) in a reliable, reproducible and observer-independent way.

Some works can be found in the literature (Badger et al., 2010; Halbfass et al., 2015; Peters et al., 2007) to characterize ablation gaps but all of them rely on visual inspection of complex 3D data by several observers. This approach can be difficult, time-consuming and inaccurate if not performed in a consistent and unbiased way. The proposed method, based on searching minimum distance paths among scar patches, overcomes most of these issues, defining gaps automatically, objectively and with high reproducibility, once a scar pattern in a LA is available. Additionally, the standard parcellation of the LA allows to regionally locate the gaps and study their distribution in different atrial areas.

The method presented in this chapter does not rely on any particular ablation technique or scar segmentation approach and it could indeed be used to quantitatively and fairly compare different options for these steps. Also, we have analysed chronic ablation lesions but our method could be applied to study acute lesions and their evolution at follow-up.

The proposed method could help to investigate the relation between electrical and anatomical gaps. However, the suitability of EAM data for gap detection and quantification is limited mainly because of the difficulty of properly correlate them with positions on the LA segmentation acquired from CMR studies. Voltage mapping does not entirely reflect scar formation (Kowalski et al., 2012) for several reasons. For instance, voltage is measured in an area and not at the infinitesimal point where the catheter is touching the wall, and it is highly sensitive to the catheter electrode configuration (Blauer et al., 2014; Josephson and Anter, 2015). The use of EAM to detect scar also requires establishing voltage thresholds for tissue classification, having the same issues as for LGE-MRI thresholds. For all these reasons, direct extrapolation of EAM data to validate LGE-MRI data should be performed with caution, in particular when the two modalities provide contradictory information.

There is high variability in PV morphology (position, orientation, size, thickness) in the whole population. Nonetheless, the proposed *RGM* index is independent of PV variations; it can then be used to compare PV from different patients. We have also found that the *RGM* is more robust

Figure 4.9: Variation of the number of gaps (left) and RGM (right) measurements with regard to the threshold used. Each color corresponds to a different patient.

to scar segmentation changes than the number of gaps, currently used in gap quantification studies. The number of gaps greatly depends on the scar pattern as can be seen in Figure 4.9 where the evolution of the two measurements with regard to five increasing thresholds is shown. Whenever the threshold increases, less tissue is classified as scar and in consequence a higher proportion of gap is expected. The RGM (right in Figure 4.9) shows this foreseen behavior while the number of gaps measure (left) increases or decreases without any clear tendency in these cases.

The proposed method has a number of limitations mostly related to the pre-processing of the data. First, it highly depends on the LA segmentation step. As mentioned before, we have decided to demonstrate the proposed gap quantification method using a threshold-based approach to detect scar even if thresholding might not be the optimal scar segmentation algorithm as shown in Karim et al. (2013). The most advanced clinical researchers working on LGE-MRI guided RFA of AF patients are currently using threshold-based methods to segment scar in the LA, as demonstrated in large studies such as the DECAAF clinical trials (Marrouche et al., 2014) and in the review paper of Pontecorboli et al. (2016). As we recently showed (Chubb et al., 2018b), thresholds are likely to differ not only between patients, but also with the time from gadolinium administration. We consider that all these aspects are outside the scope of our work. Therefore, we have used a segmentation algorithm that could be easily translated to clinical routine for its daily use. The choice was to use the 3.3 SD threshold to detect scar, validated in Harrison et al. (2014) in the first histological study of this type. However, we recognise that their confidence intervals for this

threshold were wide. For this reason, we adapted the methodology to simultaneously use a range of thresholds from 2 to 6 SD for the computation of the RGM_{NAUC} . However, the selection of the most suitable threshold limits and the number of thresholds considered in between needs to be better investigated.

Another important limitation of the current implementation of the method is the requirement of a 4 PV configuration in the left atria for its regional parcellation. This is the most common topology (around 70% (Marom et al., 2004; Prasanna et al., 2014)) but the presence of common trunks or extra PVs is relatively common as well. In our dataset, 90% of the cases (45 LAs) had 4 PVs while the remaining 10% (5 LAs) showed some of the topological peculiarities previously mentioned.

An inaccurate parcellation of the LA could lead to incorrect cutting lines and the impossibility of finding a close encircling path around a PV. In our study, this type of error was identified only in 2 PVs, out of the 180 analysed (from 45 cases).

4.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, we presented a methodology to detect and quantify incomplete ablation lesions (or gaps) after RF-PVI in a reliable, reproducible and observer-independent way. An unambiguous definition of the gap as the minimal portion of healthy tissue around a PV was provided, and showed beneficial specially in complex scenarios where scar lesions are patchy and not continuous. Based on this objective definition of gap, we proposed a quantitative and highly reproducible index, the RGM , which represents the proportion of the vein not encircled by scar (i.e. portion of incompleteness). Furthermore, a standard parcellation of the LA was used allowing for regional comparison across patients. Additionally, a full characterization of the gaps was provided in terms of their number, position and length. With the aim of reducing the influence of the scar segmentation process, we proposed a multi-threshold scheme for scar segmentation and the integration of results in the RGM_{NAUC} measure.

We showed the suitability of the proposed method to quantify lesion completeness/incompleteness after PVI and it could therefore be used to compare novel ablation catheters or techniques at full vein isolation efficiency in a consistent and fair way. Our method could also be used to detect target

ablation regions, previously to a redo procedure, favouring its planning and potentially lowering its duration.

Clinical applications

Introduction – During this thesis, we have applied the developed techniques to investigate different clinical questions: we used the gap quantification method described in Chapter 4 to inspect the regional distribution of ablation gaps in a population of 50 AF patients who underwent radiofrequency PVI, and to analyse the reproducibility of LGE-MRI scar imaging with respect to imaging parameters; we used the consistent parcellation method in the SUM pipeline to inspect the regional distribution of fibrosis in AF patients; we investigated the reproducibility of AF related measurements such as scar extent and location when manual techniques are employed to segment the LA; and we developed a registration-based framework to inspect the relation between multi-modal data such as electroanatomical maps and LGE-MRI data.

This chapter includes adapted content from the following publications:

1. **Nuñez-Garcia, M.**, Camara, O., O’Neill, M. D., Razavi, R., Chubb, H., and Butakoff, C. (2018). *Mind the gap: quantification of incomplete ablation patterns after pulmonary vein isolation using minimum path search*. *Medical Image Analysis*, 51, 1–12.
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3. Chubb, H., Karim, R., Roujol, S., **Nuñez-Garcia, M.**, Williams, S.E., Whitaker, J., Harrison, J., Butakoff, C., Camara, O., Chiribiri, A. and Schaeffter, T., 2018. *The reproducibility of late gadolinium enhancement cardiovascular magnetic resonance imaging of post-ablation atrial scar: a cross-over study*. *Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance*, 20(1), p.21.
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5.1 Gap quantification population analysis

The gap quantification framework presented in Chapter 4 was applied to a population of 50 AF patients undergoing first time pulmonary vein isolation (PVI) ablation for atrial fibrillation. The statistical analysis of the results showed that the LIPV and the LSPV had significantly lower and higher RGM_{NAUC} and number of gaps, respectively. No statistically significant difference was found when considered as ipsilateral (same side) pairs. The detailed parcellation of the LA permitted to determine that the LAA ridge was the part of the LA with the highest occurrence of gaps in our population. This type of information can be very useful for the optimization and objective assessment of PVI interventions.

Data description

Fifty patients between January 2014 and January 2016 at St Thomas' Hospital (London, UK) were included in this study. All of them provided written and informed consent and the study was approved by the National Research Ethics Service (South London Research Ethics Committee reference 08/H0802/68). For patients with a diagnosis of paroxysmal AF and in sinus rhythm, a point-by-point wide area circumferential ablation (WACA) achieving PVI was performed using 8Fr irrigated SmartTouch catheter (Biosense Webster), or 8Fr irrigated TactiCath catheter (St Jude). Target ablation parameters were $>5g$ for at least 15 seconds per RF delivery location. Power was 30W throughout except on the posterior wall, where it was limited to 25W. For patients presenting with persistent AF, a WACA was performed followed by additional ablation lesion sets (mitral line, roof line, inferior posterior line, complex fractionated electrogram ablation) as a step-wise ablation.

Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (CMR) imaging was performed on a 1.5 T MR-scanner (Ingenua, Philips Healthcare, Best, Netherlands) three months after the ablation. 3D inversion recovery spoiled gradient echo acquisition was performed with coverage to include the whole LA in axial orientation, using the following MR acquisition parameters: TR 5.5 ms, TE 3.0 ms, flip angle 25° , low-high k-space ordering, respiratory and ECG-triggering (end atrial diastole, maximum 120 ms acquisition window), $1.3 \times 1.3 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ (typically 50 slices per acquisition), SPIR fat suppression. Gadolinium-Based Contrast Agents (GBCA) dose was 0.2 ml/kg Gadovist (Bayer HealthCare

Table 5.1: Mean and standard deviation of the RGM_{NAUC} , the gap length (GL), and number (#) of gaps detected in our dataset. Statistically significant differences (in bold) were found in the LIPV and LSPV. RSPV = Right Superior PV; RIPV = Right Inferior PV; LIPV = Left Inferior PV; LSPV = Left Superior PV.

	<i>Independent-encirclement</i>				<i>Joint-encirclement</i>	
	RSPV	RIPV	LIPV	LSPV	Right	Left
Mean RGM_{NAUC}	0.303	0.331	0.208	0.384	0.261	0.249
SD RGM_{NAUC}	0.269	0.317	0.207	0.271	0.224	0.199
Mean GL (mm)	17.69	14.85	8.66	16.37	27.74	21.86
SD GL (mm)	14.72	12.97	7.42	10.76	23.22	16.01
Mean # gaps	1.56	1.36	1.16	1.73	2.34	2.00
SD # gaps	0.85	0.89	0.64	0.81	1.63	1.20

Pharmaceuticals, Berlin, Germany). Acquisitions were commenced 30 min post gadolinium-based contrast agent administration (Chubb et al., 2018a). A gated magnetic resonance angiogram (GMRA) 3D dataset was also acquired as a high contrast template. The acquisition was commenced 90 seconds after the start of a slow infusion of GBCA at 0.3ml/second (Groarke et al., 2014) with the same coverage and parameters (previously mentioned) as the subsequent LGE acquisitions.

Results

The amount and regional distribution of gaps in the whole population were analysed in two phases: firstly, we studied the RGM_{NAUC} and the quantity of gaps in each search area; and secondly, the specific position and length of gaps in the 28 standard regions in our atlas was inspected. We additionally evaluated the differences in gap quantification obtained with single- vs multi-threshold approaches for scar segmentation.

Table 5.1 shows, for each (or pair of) PV, statistics (mean and standard deviation) of the RGM_{NAUC} , the average (of multiple thresholds) gap length and number of gaps. Similarly, the left column in Figure 5.1 shows the boxplot corresponding to the RGM_{NAUC} and to the average number of gaps (top and bottom in the figure, respectively) in the same search areas. It can be seen that, in our dataset, the pulmonary veins with higher and lower RGM_{NAUC} were the LSPV and LIPV, respectively. The two halves of the LA, analysed following the *joint-encirclement* approach, exhibit very similar measurements. Differences across distributions were tested using two-sample t-test: the null hypothesis was that RGM_{NAUC} distribution was the same for a given PV comparing to the remaining ones. Statistically significant differences were found for the LIPV ($p = 0.0052$) and the LSPV

Figure 5.1: Left: gap quantification provided by the proposed multi-threshold approach: distributions of the RGM_{NAUC} (top) and the average number of gaps (bottom) around the different veins. On the right, results corresponding to a single threshold approach (3.3 SD): distributions of the RGM (top) and the number of gaps (bottom).

Figure 5.2: Histograms of the RGM_{NAUC} (normalized area under the curve of regional gap measurement for multiple-threshold segmentations) in all search areas, representing the amount of patients within a given RGM_{NAUC} interval. Ideal ablation should locate most patients in the first bin (0.0 to 0.1 RGM_{NAUC}), in a skewed right shape.

($p = 0.029$). On the other hand, there were not statistically significant differences between right or left PVs when using the *joint-encirclement* approach ($p = 0.80$). Regarding the quantity of gaps around each PV, the LSPV and the LIPV were the veins with the highest and lowest occurrence of gaps, respectively. Likewise in the case of the RGM_{NAUC} measurement, a t-test analysis revealed significant differences on the number of gaps with regard to the same veins (LIPV, $p = 0.0059$; LSPV, $p = 0.0092$). The *joint-encirclement* approach estimated more gaps on the right half of the LA but differences with the left side were not significant ($p = 0.27$).

Figure 5.2 shows the distribution of patients within each RGM_{NAUC} in-

Figure 5.3: Results from the regional patient population study: for each region, the top, middle and bottom row show the percentage of patients with at least one gap, the total number of gaps, and the mean gap length, respectively. The first two columns correspond to the *independent-encirclement* approach (superior and inferior veins are shown separately because of the overlapping regions) and the third column corresponds to the *joint-encirclement* approach. Black regions represent the ones excluded in each approach.

terval. The first bin in the histogram represents patients with RGM_{NAUC} between 0 and 0.1 (i.e. complete or almost complete encirclement) that would correspond to a more favorable outcome of the PVI procedure. It can be observed that while the LIPV has the highest number of patients with that value of RGM_{NAUC} , the LSPV has the lowest.

Results of the regional analysis using the single threshold ($T = 3.3$ SD) segmentation approach can be seen in Figure 5.3. Different 2D SUM plots display the regional distribution of the percentage of patients with at least one gap, the total number of gaps and their length in the whole population. It can be observed that the region with the highest occurrence of gaps is in

between the LSPV and the LAA (LAA ridge).

We also analysed the impact of the chosen segmentation threshold on RGM values. For all thresholds under study, both LIPV and LSPV were significant ($p < 0.05$) besides the LSPV when the threshold was 3.3 SD ($p = 0.057$), which suggests that, even when the distributions change according to the threshold, the statistical differences remain. Figure 5.1 shows a boxplot representation of the RGM distributions corresponding to the multi-threshold approach (left) and to a single-threshold approach with $T = 3.3$ SD. The number of gaps had a less stable behaviour than RGM values: it was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) only for some thresholds in the LIPV (3.3 SD, 4 SD) and the LSPV (2 SD, 4 SD, 5 SD). In the *joint-encirclement* approach any difference between right and left PVs was found statistically significant in any case.

Finally, the obtained gap quantification indices were compared with the clinical outcome of AF recurrence at follow-up. Recurrence of AF was present in only 11 patients (24%) who were brought back to the hospital for a redo RFA procedure where reconnection (i.e. electrical conduction recovery after a previous successful isolation) in each PV was assessed. Reconnection was identified in 22 PVs (12%): 8 cases in RSPV, 5 cases in LSPV, 5 cases in RIPV, and 4 cases in LIPV. As mentioned before, a wide area circumferential ablation (WACA) was performed (i.e. *joint-encirclement* approach) and it is therefore expected to find healthy tissue in the carinas (region between ipsilateral veins) that would increase the RGM if the *independent-encirclement* approach is considered. However, during the procedure and at the clinicians discretion an intervenous line was performed in 18 patients. This was generally performed in the case of more difficult vein isolation in order to achieve the optimal clinical result. For this reason, the final gap measure was taken as the minimum among the corresponding *independent-* and *joint-encirclement* approaches (e.g. $\text{final-}RGM_{NAUC}(\text{RSPV}) = \min(RGM_{NAUC}(\text{RSPV}), RGM_{NAUC}(\text{Right PVs}))$) since we do not know (a priori) which of the two metrics is the smallest one. Non-significant ($p = 0.523$) slightly higher RGM_{NAUC} values were found among the two groups: mean and SD of 0.258 ± 0.214 and 0.222 ± 0.210 for reconnected and not reconnected PVs, respectively. A similar result was obtained when using the single threshold ($T = 3.3\text{SD}$) approach: 0.204 ± 0.226 vs. 0.156 ± 0.182 , $p = 0.328$.

All steps in the pipeline were computationally in real-time besides mesh standardization, which required manual interaction, and the non-rigid reg-

istration. The execution time of the registration was 18 ± 7 min on a desktop computer (Intel i5 3.3 GHz CPU and 16 GB RAM).

Discussion

In the studied population, the LIPV and LSPV showed the lowest and highest *RGM* values, respectively. The higher *RGM* at the LSPV may be partially accounted for by the transverse imaging acquisition plane, with lower resolution between slices. The roof of the LA lies in the transverse plane, and both the imaging and accurate segmentation of these regions, and hence scar detection, are more challenging. The analysis of the gap probability map (Figure 5.3, top) revealed that the most common gap location is the area between the LSPV and the LAA (LAA ridge): almost 70% of cases had a gap in that region. In addition to the imaging concerns mentioned above, the elevated number of gaps in that area could also be explained by the presence of a thicker myocardium and the associated difficulty to access with a catheter leading to loss of contact and therefore to non-transmural lesions (Cabrera et al., 2009; Galand et al., 2016). The importance of the transmural of lesions was recently demonstrated by Glover et al. (2018). Our results are in agreement with the investigation of Furnkranz et al. (2010) that found the higher probability of having conduction gaps in the same area (LAA ridge) after cryoballoon ablation. However, these findings contrast with those of more recent contact force-guided ablation studies with invasive assessment (Kautzner et al., 2015) where the authors did not find a higher proportion of conduction gaps in that area. In contrast to the findings in Halbfass et al. (2015) showing that the left PVs had a significantly higher amount of ablation lesions compared with the right PVs (83% vs 34%, $p < 0.001$), we did not find significant differences between left and right PVs when considered as ipsilateral pairs. Importantly, the authors used cryoballoon ablation and argued that it is much easier to properly place the cryoballoon into the left PV ostia than into the right ostia which may not be the case in RF ablation.

The absence of a significant relationship in this study between detection of gaps in the CMR-derived ablation lines and recurrence questions the immediate relevance of post-ablation atrial scar imaging. This finding is supported by some recent studies (Harrison et al., 2015b; Spragg et al., 2012), but at odds with others which have demonstrated a significant relationship (Badger et al., 2010; Bisbal et al., 2014; Peters et al., 2009; Taclas et al., 2010). However, it is important to review carefully those prior pub-

lications with positive findings, as they themselves have clearly delineated the limits of the relationship. For example, Peters et al. (2009) found that the degree of scarring around only the RIPV was significant in predicting recurrence, thought to be likely to reflect the technical difficulty in isolating that vein and propensity of triggers to arise from that location. Similarly, Badger et al. (2010) found that only 10 out of 144 (7%) of patients had complete scar encirclement of all PVs, but that there were no recurrences in this group, a statistically significant finding in a small subgroup. The metrics used to assess gaps in this study are arguably more rigorous, but the overall proportion without a gap in both vein pairs encirclement is similar (7% of acquisitions had $> 99\%$ PV encirclement of both veins), and in this case was not associated with recurrence.

In this work, we did not compute the RGM for the pre-procedural cases since a comparison between pre- and post-procedural LA scar was already performed in Chubb et al. (2018b) on the same dataset. In pre-procedural cases, a very small proportion of the LA surface was designated as scar and there was a very weak overall correlation between the proportion of pre-ablation scar and the percentage of post-ablation atrial scar ($R^2 = 0.024$, $p = 0.02$ across all acquisitions). Pre-ablation scar location was therefore interpreted to be unrelated to post-ablation scar location and of minimal significance in further assessment.

5.2 Reproducibility of post-ablation atrial scar LGE-CMR imaging

Abstract

The assessment of post-ablation atrial scar (PAAS) using late gadolinium enhancement cardiac magnetic resonance (LGE-CMR) imaging has been used for almost a decade (McGann et al., 2011; Peters et al., 2007) but its reproducibility has never been formally quantified. An assessment of reproducibility is crucial from both a clinical and research perspective as the use of the technique becomes increasingly mainstream (Akoum et al., 2015; Bisbal et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2015a; Hunter et al., 2013; Taclas et al., 2010). Recent studies of PAAS have tended to use very different scanning parameters, including different slice thickness (2 - 2.5 mm (Akoum et al., 2015; Badger et al., 2010; Bisbal et al., 2014) to 4 mm (Harrison et al., 2015a; Hunter et al., 2013; Taclas et al., 2010)), different gadolinium based contrast agents (GBCAs) and doses (varying from 0.1 - 0.4 mmol/kg of Multihance (Badger et al., 2010), Magnevist (Hunter et al., 2013; Taclas et al., 2010), or Gadovist (Bisbal et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2015a)), and different scanner bore strengths (1.5T, 3T, or both). This cross-over study is the first to investigate the impact of these variations in detection and designation of PAAS.

Forty subjects undergoing first time ablation for atrial fibrillation (AF) had detailed CMR assessment of PAAS. Following baseline pre-ablation scan, two scans (separated by 48 hours) were performed at three months post-ablation. Each scan session included 3D LGE acquisition at 10, 20 and 30 min post administration of gadolinium-based contrast agent (GBCA). Subjects were allocated at second scan post-ablation to identical imaging parameters (“Repro”, n=10), 3T scanner (“3T”, n=10), half-slice thickness (“Half-slice”, n=10) or half GBCA dose (“Half-gad”, n=10). As there is no single established metric of PAAS imaging for comparison in assessment of reproducibility, some having looked to determine scar burden and location (Badger et al., 2010; Hunter et al., 2013; Karim et al., 2013), while others having sought to determine the presence of gaps in the ablation line (Bisbal et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2015a), new methods were developed specifically for this study. In this section we focus on the Pulmonary Vein Encirclement (PVE) metric which is the inverse of the Relative Gap Measure (RGM) explained in Chapter 4, i.e. $PVE = 1 - RGM$.

Results showed that at 20 and 30 min, inter-scan reproducibility was good to excellent (PVE coefficient of variation at 20 min and 30 min was 0.13 and 0.04, respectively, for “Repro” group). Changes in imaging parameters, especially reduced GBCA dose, reduced inter-scan reproducibility, but for most measures remained good to excellent. There was no significant relationship between indices of PAAS and AF recurrence. In this study, we concluded that PAAS imaging is a reproducible finding (imaging should be performed at least 20 min post-GBCA administration) but the clinical implications of these findings remain to be established in the absence of a simple correlation with arrhythmia outcome.

Data description

Between January 2014 and January 2016, all patients undergoing routine MR imaging prior to first-time AF ablation procedure were approached to join the study. Forty subjects provided written and informed consent and the study was approved by the National Research Ethics Service (South London Research Ethics Committee reference 08/H0802/68).

Two experienced operators performed all catheter ablation procedures under general anaesthesia using Carto3 (Biosense Webster/Johnson&Johnson, Irvine, California, USA) electroanatomic mapping system, with the exception of 8 procedures performed using EnSite Velocity (St Jude Medical, St. Paul, Minnesota, USA). For patients with a diagnosis of paroxysmal AF and in sinus rhythm, a point-by-point wide area circumferential ablation (WACA) achieving pulmonary vein isolation (PVI) was performed using 8Fr irrigated SmartTouch catheter (Biosense Webster), or 8Fr irrigated TactiCath catheter (St Jude Medical). Target ablation parameters were >5 g for at least 15 s per radiofrequency (RF) delivery location. Power was 30 W throughout except on the posterior wall, where it was limited to 25 W. Procedural endpoint was defined as PV isolation as confirmed on entry block. For patients presenting with persistent AF, a WACA was performed followed by additional ablation lesion sets (mitral line, roof line, inferior posterior line, complex fractionated electrogram ablation) as a step-wise ablation.

All patients underwent further CMR imaging on two occasions following clinically indicated catheter ablation for AF (see flowchart in Figure 5.4). The first post-ablation CMR scan (Scan 1) was performed at approximately three months after the ablation procedure, regardless of rhythm or arrhyth-

Figure 5.4: Flow chart of subject allocation and number of scan acquisitions performed.

mia recurrence, and was performed using standard acquisition parameters (see below). A second scan session (Scan 2) was performed 2 days later. Subjects were allocated to scan 2 in 3T scanner or the same 1.5T scanner. 3T scanner availability was limited, precluding randomisation of allocation, but the allocation ($n=10$) was performed without reference to patient outcome or demographics. The remaining patients were randomised in equal ratios to one of three different imaging parameter groups for scan 2: repeat scan with identical acquisition parameters (“Repro” group, $n=10$), repeat with half dose of GBCA (“Half-gad” group, $n=10$), or repeat with half-slice thickness (“Half-slice” group, $n=10$).

Methods

All CMR imaging was performed on a 1.5T MR-scanner (Ingenia, Philips Healthcare, Best, Netherlands), except for those allocated to 3T scanner for scan 2. All patients underwent detailed assessment at pre-procedural CMR scan, including LA volumes and function, and 3D LGE assessment of baseline left atrial fibrosis. Cine imaging was performed in an end-expiratory breathhold using a standard multislice bSSFP technique (effective TR 2.7

msec, TE 1.3 msec, $1.4 \times 1.4 \text{mm}^2$ in-plane, slice thickness 10 mm, 50 phases). 3D inversion recovery spoiled gradient echo (LGE) acquisition was performed with coverage to include the whole of the LA in axial orientation (TR 5.5msec, TE 3.0msec, flip angle 25° , low-high k-space ordering, respiratory and ECG-triggering (end atrial diastole, maximum 120 msec acquisition window, respiratory navigator leading with gating window 5mm), $1.3 \times 1.3 \times 4 \text{mm}^3$ (typically 50 slices per acquisition, reconstructed to $0.94 \times 0.94 \times 2 \text{mm}^3$), SPIR fat suppression, pixel bandwidth 540Hz, phase-encoding direction AP, parallel imaging: SENSE P-reduction (AP) factor 2, 32 channel phased array digital receiver coil). Average acquisition window onset was 296 ± 40 msec post R-wave, and end at 398 ± 39 msec. GBCA dose for standard acquisition was 0.2mmol/kg Gadovist (Bayer HealthCare Pharmaceuticals, Berlin, Germany). Respiratory gating artefact was minimised using an obtuse angulation of the navigator at the extreme right posterior aspect of the diaphragm, minimising excitation of pulmonary venous blood flow.

Scan 1 (post-procedure) was performed using the same 3D LGE acquisition parameters as the baseline scan, and 3 LGE-CMR datasets were acquired, timed to start at 10, 20 and 30 minutes after GBCA administration.

Scan 2 (post-procedure) was performed with the following specific modifications of the baseline scan, with acquisitions again performed at 10, 20 and 30 minutes post GBCA administration:

1. Reproducibility (“Repro”, n=10): identical parameters to Scan 1.
2. Half-gadolinium dose (“Half-gad”, n=10): 0.1mmol/kg of Gadovist.
3. Half-slice thickness (“Half-slice”, n=10): the acquired voxel size was reduced to $1.3 \times 1.3 \times 2 \text{mm}^3$ (reconstructed $0.625 \times 0.625 \times 1 \text{mm}^3$). Field of view remained unchanged to cover the whole of the left atrium, and therefore approximately 90-100 slices were acquired, doubling the acquisition duration.
4. 3T scanner (“3T”, n=10): scans were performed on Philips Achieva 3T scanner and parameters were matched to those for 1.5T scanning as closely as possible (TR 4.0 msec, TE 2.0 msec, slice thickness 4mm, pixel bandwidth 620Hz, acquired voxel size $1.3 \times 1.3 \times 4 \text{mm}^3$).

An ECG-triggered magnetic resonance angiogram (GMRA) 3D dataset was also acquired at each scan as a high contrast template, delineating the LA

Table 5.2: Nomenclature of the image acquisitions. Comparison between two acquisitions i and j is termed $C_{i,j}$. Acq = acquisition.

			Post-ablation Scan 1			Post-ablation Scan 2		
			10 min	20 min	30 min	10 min	20 min	30 min
			Acq ₁	Acq ₂	Acq ₃	Acq ₄	Acq ₅	Acq ₆
Baseline scan	20 min	Acq ₀	C _{0,1}	C _{0,2}	C _{0,3}	C _{0,4}	C _{0,5}	C _{0,6}
Post-ablation scan 1	10 min	Acq ₁	-	C _{1,2}	C _{1,3}	C _{1,4}	C _{1,5}	C _{1,6}
	20 min	Acq ₂	-	-	C _{2,3}	C _{2,4}	C _{2,5}	C _{2,6}
	30 min	Acq ₃	-	-	-	C _{3,4}	C _{3,5}	C _{3,6}
Post-ablation scan 2	10 min	Acq ₄	-	-	-	-	C _{4,5}	C _{4,6}
	20 min	Acq ₅	-	-	-	-	-	C _{5,6}
	30 min	Acq ₆	-	-	-	-	-	-

endocardial border with the same coverage as the subsequent LGE acquisitions.

For all subjects a semi-automated segmentation of the LA was obtained from the GMRA images with a standard region-growing segmentation technique initialized by manually placed seeds, available in the ITK-SNAP⁵ software (Yushkevich et al., 2006). The segmentation was then rigidly registered independently to each LGE acquisition of the same imaging session (Acq₁, Acq₂, Acq₃, see Table 5.2 for nomenclature). For the subsequent imaging session (Scan 2), the MRA acquisition at post-ablation Scan 1 was registered to the GMRA acquisition of post-ablation Scan 2, which was itself then registered to each subsequent LGE acquisition (Acq₄, Acq₅, Acq₆). Through this method, an identical atrial shell could be used for all six acquisitions. The LGE-CMR volume was interrogated using a maximum intensity projection (MIP) technique, 1 mm inside endocardial shell and 3 mm beyond endocardial shell, and a single signal intensity (SI) value was assigned to each triangular face of the generated LA mesh.

A histologically validated threshold of 3.3 standard deviations (SD) above the mean blood pool intensity was used to detect scar (Harrison et al., 2014). After that, pulmonary vein encirclement (PVE), an objective measurement of the proportion of the WACA line that is occupied by uninterrupted scar was computed as 1 - RGM, where RGM corresponds to the Relative Gap Measure that we proposed in Nuñez-Garcia et al. (2018) (see Figure 5.5).

Recurrence of AF post-ablation was defined as a recurrence of AF (>30s), or episodes of atrial tachycardia or atrial flutter, in line with HRS/EHRA guidelines (Calkins et al., 2012). Follow-up was at 3 months post-ablation, with symptom review, 24 h tape and 12-lead ECG performed. Subsequently,

⁵www.itksnap.org

Figure 5.5: Illustration of pulmonary vein encirclement (PVE) computation. Scar and healthy atrial myocardium are shown on the surface of the LA shell in red and blue, respectively. Antero-superior (**A**) and postero-lateral (**B**) view of the LA. The computed encircling path is shown in white (gaps) and with a yellow dashed line (non-gap). RSPV = right superior PV; RIPV = right inferior PV; LIPV = left inferior PV; LSPV = left superior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage.

patients were typically reviewed at 6 and 12 months after the index procedure, and yearly thereafter. A 12-lead ECG \pm holter monitor was performed at each review, in the absence of reported symptoms. If symptoms were reported, patients underwent 12-lead ECG, Holter monitor or event monitor assessment, according to symptom frequency. A blanking period of three months was employed post ablation and the %LA PAAS and %PVE were assessed against the binary outcome of recurrence of atrial arrhythmia. Where a repeat LA ablation procedure was performed, the presence or absence of electrical reconnection of each PV pair was recorded and corresponding PVE assessed.

Results

Figure 5.6 shows an example of LGE-CMR images, and corresponding LA shells with detected scar, from the “Repro” group (i.e. Scan 1 and Scan 2 were performed using identical acquisition parameters). The last row additionally shows LGE-CMR and LA shell corresponding to the pre-ablation scan. Note the poor reproducibility for acquisitions at 10 min, particularly Scan 1, and the agreement between Acq₂, Acq₃, Acq₅, and Acq₆.

Figure 5.7 (top row) shows the relationship between total scar burden and PVE. It is clear that there is a significant relationship between PVE and scar burden but it should be noted that scar burden is not the only determinant of PVE: in some cases complete PVE may be observed in the presence of low

Figure 5.6: Examples of raw images and corresponding scar shells for a single subject. In this example, Scans 1 and 2 were performed using identical standard acquisition parameters (i.e. “Repro” group), with acquisitions performed at 10 min, 20 min, and 30 min post gadolinium administration. Upper six panels show single representative slices of the 3D LGE-CMR. The six panels below show corresponding scar shells, normalised according to blood pool. The bottom two panels show the baseline scan, performed 20 min after GBCA administration one month prior to ablation. Acq: acquisition. LSPV = left superior PV; LIPV = left inferior pulmonary vein; RSPV = right superior pulmonary vein; RIPV = right inferior pulmonary vein; LAA = left atrial appendage; SD = standard deviation; BP = blood pool.

(<20%) total scar burden, whilst in others a much larger proportion of the shell may be ascribed to scar status without complete PVE. PVE was significantly lower at 20 min than 30 min ($76.4 \pm 21.9\%$ versus $82.3 \pm 18.1\%$, $p < 0.001$). Mean bias was -5.9% (95% confidence interval -29.8% to $+18.0\%$) (Figure 5.7, bottom left). For inter-scan comparisons of the acquisitions

Figure 5.7: Impact of time from GBCA administration (top row) and reproducibility of PVE measurements (bottom row). Red lines show mean bias \pm 95% confidence interval.

with identical imaging parameters (“Repro”), the within-subject coefficient of variation (WCV) (calculated using a root mean square method (Quan and Shih, 1996)) was 0.126 at 20 min ($C_{2,5}$ [Repro]), improving to 0.045 at 30 min ($C_{3,6}$ [Repro], $p = 0.02$), reflecting a high degree of reproducibility at both time points (Figure 5.8, top left). When different parameters were used for the second scan, the reproducibility remained acceptable. With a half dose of GBCA, PVE was significantly higher at the two time point compared to standard imaging (standard: $70.7 \pm 26.0\%$ versus half gad: $84.7 \pm 15.6\%$, $p < 0.001$), but there was no significant inter-scan difference in PVE for “Half Slice” or “3T” ($p = 0.65$ and 0.35 , respectively) (Figure 5.7). Inter-scan intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) at 20 and 30 min for the “Half-gad” group were 0.458 and 0.618, for the “Half-slice” group were 0.626 and 0.781 and for the “3T” group were 0.697 and 0.809 respectively. For comparison, the ICCs in the “Repro” group were 0.774 and 0.876, respectively.

Follow-up time post ablation was for a median 417 days (IQR 285 - 628 days), and in total there were 13 patients (33%) with a recurrence of AF

Figure 5.8: Reproducibility of pulmonary vein encirclement (PVE) measurements. Bland-Altman plots demonstrate reproducibility of measurements performed at 20 min post GBCA ($c_{2,5}$, open squares) and 30 min post GBCA ($c_{3,6}$, closed squares). Red lines show mean bias $\pm 95\%$ confidence interval.

or tachycardia. Eleven patients elected to undergo a further ablation procedure, with two patients undergoing conservative management. There was also no significant difference in average PVE between groups (no recurrence: 81.7% (IQR 63.2-96.3%), recurrence: 86.1% (IQR 73.2-95.4%), $p = 0.10$). Electrical reconnection of at least one PV pair was confirmed in 10 of the 11 subjects that underwent repeat ablation, and sites of reconnection versus respective PVE are shown in Fig. 5.9. There was no significant relationship between PVE and likelihood of electrical isolation of the vein pair, subjects could demonstrate very high or even complete PVE on CMR imaging, but still have electrical reconnection of the vein pair.

Figure 5.9: Relationship between percentage PVE and electrical reconnection.

Discussion

The key findings of this study can be summarised as follows: (1) there is good to excellent inter-scan reproducibility of thresholded PAAS imaging when identical imaging parameters are used; (2) reproducibility of PAAS imaging is better for acquisitions performed later (30 min) after GBCA injection; (3) reproducibility of PAAS imaging is significantly affected by the use of different imaging parameters, particularly different doses of GBCA, but remains acceptable when processed appropriately; (4) there was no significant relationship between PAAS summary indices and AF recurrence.

A change in the GBCA had the greatest impact upon reproducibility, with more PAAS detected, particularly at earlier timepoints post-GBCA administration. However, poor inter-scan reproducibility does not imply worse imaging with the altered parameter: reduced GBCA dose may improve PAAS detection and warrants further investigation, in line with recent ventricular scar LGE imaging studies (D'Angelo et al., 2017). Imaging quality was found to be poorer when the 3D LGE sequence was acquired at less than 20 min after GBCA administration, and this was reflected in very low markers of reproducibility for comparisons involving acquisitions at 10 min post-GBCA administration. A greater area of thresholded scar was consistently identified on scans acquired at 30 min than at 20 min. Moreover, on assessment of PVE, the measurements were significantly more reproducible at 30 min, perhaps reflecting the higher contrast-to-noise ratio observed at this time point and the increased time for equilibration of contrast.

The absence of a significant relationship in this study between detection of gaps in the CMR-derived ablation line and recurrence questions the immediate relevance of PAAS imaging. This finding is in keeping with some recent studies (Harrison et al., 2015a; Spragg et al., 2012), but at odds with others which have demonstrated a significant relationship (Badger et al., 2010; Bisbal et al., 2014; Peters et al., 2009; Taclas et al., 2010). However, it is important to review carefully those prior publications with positive findings, as they themselves have clearly delineated the limits of the relationship. For example, in one of the earliest studies of PAAS in 2009, Peters et al. found that the degree of scarring around only the RIPV was significant in predicting recurrence, thought to be likely to reflect the technical difficulty in isolating that vein and propensity of triggers to arise from that location. Similarly, in 2010 Badger et al. found that only 10 out of 144 (7%) patients had complete scar encirclement of all PVs, but that there were no recurrences in this group, a statistically significant finding in a small subgroup. The metrics used to assess gaps in this study are arguably more rigorous, but the overall proportion without a gap in both vein pairs' encirclement is similar (7% of acquisitions had > 99% PVE of both veins), and in this case was not associated with recurrence. However, the interplay of interruption of the continuity of the PVI lesion set and AF recurrence is a complex one: many gaps will not necessarily lead to recurrence of arrhythmia, whilst very small gaps may be sufficient for electrical reconnection. Further work is clearly required to fully understand the relationship between electrical and imaging gaps in scar post-ablation, and the impacts upon AF recurrence.

This study presents the following limitations. First, there is no gold standard for assessment of accuracy of scar detection and delineation. Manual segmentation was considered, as has been performed in previous studies (Karim et al., 2013), but the inter- and intraobserver variability was high for this subjective measure. Additionally, a typical concern of the scar detection technique using a maximum intensity projection, is that adjacent bright structures such as the aorta may be interrogated. The processing technique, using an endocardial mask based upon the high contrast GMRA, aimed to minimise the contamination of signal from beyond the atrial wall, but there remains the possibility that reproducibility measures may have been increased by mis-interrogation of static structures.

5.3 Preferential regional distribution of fibrosis in patients with AF

Abstract

The presence of myocardial atrial fibrosis is part of the remodelling associated to atrial fibrillation (AF) as a response to inflammation, stretch or overload imposed by risk factors or by aging (Fabritz et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2004). Left atrial (LA) fibrosis can be identified by late gadolinium enhancement cardiac magnetic resonance (LGE-CMR) but there is limited information about anatomical fibrosis distribution in the LA. The aim of this study was to determine whether there is a preferential spatial distribution of fibrosis in the left atrium in patients with AF. A 3-Tesla LGE-CMR was performed in 113 consecutive patients referred for AF ablation. Images were post-processed and analysed using ADAS-AF software (Galgo Medical), which allows fibrosis identification in 3D colour-coded shells. A regional consistent LA parcellation was applied to divide the atrial wall into 12 segments and the presence and amount of fibrosis in each segment was obtained for analysis. After exclusions for artefacts and insufficient image quality, 76 LGE-MRI images (68%) were suitable for fibrosis analysis. Segments closest to the left inferior pulmonary vein, had significantly higher fibrosis ($40.42\% \pm 23.96$ and $25.82\% \pm 21.24$, respectively; $p < 0.001$), compared with other segments. Segments in the anterior wall contained the lowest fibrosis ($2.54\% \pm 5.78$ and $3.82\% \pm 11.59$, respectively; $p < 0.001$). In our dataset of AF patients, the fibrotic area was preferentially located at the posterior wall and floor around the antrum of the left inferior pulmonary vein.

Data description

A cohort of 113 consecutive patients with AF referred for a first ablation procedure in the Hospital Clínic (Barcelona) between May 2011 and March of 2015 were included in the study. 3D-LGE images were acquired 20 min after an intravenous bolus injection of 0.2mmol/kg gadobutrol (Gadovist, BayerShering, Germany) in a 3-Tesla LGE-CMR scanner (Magnetom Trio, Siemens Healthcare, Germany) using a 3D free-breathing navigator and an electrocardiogram-gated inversion recovery gradient-echo sequence applied in axial orientation. Voxel size was $1.25 \times 1.25 \times 2.5 \text{ mm}^3$. Seventy six

Figure 5.10: Pipeline for regional fibrosis quantification identified with LGE-CMR. From left to right: (1) manual delineation of the LA and mapping of LGE-MRI intensities; (2) extraction of LA surface and tissue classification based on the image intensity ratio (IIR); (3) automatic LA parcellation and quantification of fibrosis percentage.

(68%) patients were finally considered for processing and analysis after exclusion of poor quality (including inadequate inversion time and artefacts).

Methods

An overview of the method can be seen in Figure 5.10. First, the left atrial wall was segmented using the ADAS-AF⁶ image post-processing software (Galgo Medical, Barcelona, Spain) by manually delineating the epicardial and endocardial LA wall contours in each axial plane. Then, a mid-myocardial (50% thickness) layer was automatically reconstructed and a 3D triangular mesh representing the LA surface was built. After manual clipping of the pulmonary veins (PV), the left atrial appendage (LAA), and the mitral valve (MV) using ADAS-AF, voxel signal intensity maps were obtained. Image intensity ratio (IIR) values, computed as the ratio between the signal intensity of each voxel and the mean LA blood pool intensity (Khurram et al., 2014), were projected into the 3D LA surface mesh and binary classified: $IIR > 1.20$ was considered fibrosis, following the study on healthy volunteers reported by Benito et al. (2016). The complete exclusion of the MV boundary was carefully inspected because it corresponds to an area of hyper-enhancement that should not be confused with fibrosis.

⁶<https://www.adas3d.com/en/adas-af-product.html>

Figure 5.11: LA surface template parcellated according to anatomical landmarks. Posterior (left) and anterior (center) view of the 3-dimensional LA surface template, and 2-dimensional representation of the unfolded LA. LSPV = left superior PV; LIPV = left inferior PV; RSPV = right superior PV; RIPV = right inferior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage.

A novel LA parcellation (12 regions, see Figure 5.11) was manually defined on a LA template mesh using the MeshLab⁷ software and following anatomical landmarks:

- Posterior wall (regions 1, 2, 3, and 4): this area is delimited by the geodesics (i.e. curve between two points on a mesh, such that the curve lies on the surface (Mitchell et al., 1987)) connecting the 4 PVs.
- Floor (regions 5 and 6): the boundaries of these two regions are the inferior posterior wall and the posterior aspect of the mitral annulus.
- Interatrial septal wall (region 7): the wall that separates the right and the left atria.
- Anterior wall (regions 8, 9, 10, 11): the boundaries are the high posterior wall, the anterior aspect of the mitral annulus, and the LAA.
- Left lateral wall (region 12): the boundaries are the anterior wall, the LAA, and the left floor.

The acquired LA surfaces were automatically parcellated using customised code (Python) in three steps: (1) each arbitrary LA was affinely and non-rigidly registered (via currents (Durrleman et al., 2014)) to the divided template mesh shown in Figure 5.11; (2) region labels were transferred to the registered atrium via closest-point mapping; (3) region labels were added to the initial (not registered) mesh. After that, the percentage of fibrosis in

⁷<http://meshlab.sourceforge.net>

Table 5.3: Regional fibrosis quantification results. * and † denote regions with significantly higher and lower fibrosis percentage, respectively.

Regions grouped	% fibrosis	Region	% fibrosis
Whole LA	10.19 ± 8.75		
Posterior wall	17.49 ± 14.06	1	16.84 ± 17.22
		2	8.80 ± 12.80
		3	40.42 ± 23.96 *
		4	13.94 ± 20.27
Floor	14.38 ± 13.83	5	25.82 ± 21.24 *
		6	7.33 ± 12.57
Septal wall	4.14 ± 6.58	7	4.14 ± 6.58
Anterior wall	3.58 ± 7.41	8	2.54 ± 5.78 †
		9	4.46 ± 10.02
		10	3.82 ± 11.59 †
		11	4.13 ± 9.33
Left lateral wall	11.83 ± 13.92	12	11.83 ± 13.92

each region was calculated as the ratio between the area classified as scar divided by the total area of each region. Continuous variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation and compared with a t-test/MannWhitney test or one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)/Kruskal-Wallis test. To compare regional fibrosis percentages between segments, we used one-way ANOVA adjusted by contrast multiplicity according to Bonferroni *post hoc* strategy. All analyses were performed using SPSS software and a p-value of 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The percentage of patients showing significant (more than 2.5% of LA surface) atrial fibrosis was 81.6%. Patients with less than 2.5% of fibrosis were excluded from the regional distribution analysis. As can be seen in Table 5.3 and Figure 5.12, the regional analysis of fibrosis in the studied population showed that fibrosis was heterogeneously distributed in the LA wall. The posterior wall and floor areas were more affected by fibrosis, with 17.49±14.06% and 14.38±13.83%, respectively. Regions 3 and 5, corresponding to the area close to the left inferior PV, had significantly more fibrosis, compared with all other regions (40.42±23.96% and 25.82±21.24%, respectively; $p < 0.001$). Regions 8 and 10 in the anterior wall contained the lowest proportion of fibrosis (2.54±5.78% and 3.82± 11.59%, respectively; $p < 0.001$). In our population, age higher than 60 years was the only clinical characteristic associated with increased percentage of LA fibrosis (95% CI -0.19% to 7.83%, $p = 0.08$), and there was no association between fi-

Figure 5.12: Results of the regional distribution of left atrial fibrosis. On the left, boxplots of the percentage of fibrosis in the studied population where colors indicate different grouped areas. On the right, mean distribution of fibrosis measured showed in the 2D unfolded LA. LSPV = left superior PV; LIPV = left inferior PV; RSPV = right superior PV; RIPV = right inferior PV; LAA = left atrial appendage.

fibrosis and other clinical characteristic such as hypertension, diabetes, AF duration, LA volume, LA sphericity, or ejection fraction.

Discussion

The observation of more prominent fibrosis around the posterior wall adjacent to the left inferior PV in patients with limited atrial remodelling is intriguing and has no obvious explanation. It could be interesting to analyse fibrosis at this location, which is anatomically close to the descending aorta, in experimental models. Permanent trauma caused by the impact of the aortic pulse on the atrial wall may potentially play a role in this fibrosis but further studies are needed to explore this observation in depth.

Identification of fibrosis is influenced by the methodology employed. Several approaches have been proposed to detect fibrosis or post-ablation scar with no consensus with respect to the most appropriate technique (Chubb et al., 2018b; Harrison et al., 2014; Karim et al., 2013; Pontecorboli et al., 2016). Clearly, discrepancies in total fibrosis amount and localization are determined by imaging parameters, image post-processing and the fibrosis detection technique employed.

Several groups have investigated the distribution of fibrosis in AF patients. For example, Oakes et al. (2009) found that, contrary to our results, the lateral wall was the most affected segment, followed by the posterior wall. These variations in fibrosis location could be explained by a less restrictive

threshold (variable threshold ranging from 2 to 4 standard deviations above the mean for healthy myocardium intensity established by an expert) that would increase the amount of fibrosis equally throughout all the atrium. Using the same algorithm for fibrosis detection in a general population of cardiology patients, [Cochet et al. \(2015\)](#) reported, a mean of fibrosis of $18.4 \pm 8.9\%$ of the LA wall. They observed that fibrosis was predominantly located at posterior wall irrespective of previous diagnosis of AF. In this case the lateral wall was the least affected segment. Taking a different approach, [Khurram et al. \(2014\)](#) proposed a normalized signal IIR method to enable a more objective comparison between individuals. Although this is the same standardization we use, in their study, the threshold in patients with AF is based on the correlation between IIR and bipolar voltage maps obtained before an ablation procedure, defining $IIR < 0.97$ as the cut-off for pathological native tissue. This threshold has higher sensitivity and lower specificity to detect fibrosis compared with the normalized $IIR < 1.20$ calculated by [Benito et al., 2016](#)) and used in this study, which was derived from a cohort of healthy young volunteers. The mean LA LGE extent in their population was $14.1 \pm 10.4\%$, significantly greater than in ours. Using the 0.97 threshold, [Fukumoto et al. \(2016\)](#) have also reported a good correlation between IIR and local conduction velocity, especially in patients with persistent AF. Although they make no reference to the different detailed locations of fibrosis, the most affected areas they observed are adjacent to the left PV antra (the septo-pulmonary bundle region) ([Fukumoto et al., 2016](#)) corresponding with segments 1, 3, and 5 in our study. In fact, these areas correspond to a change in direction and thickness of fibres coming from the septo-pulmonary bundle that could make it more susceptible to remodelling.

The use of a restrictive threshold, $IIR < 1.20$, to detect fibrotic tissue is the main limitation of our approach. Small changes in any threshold of a continuous variable might result in large changes in the percentage and location of fibrosis; nevertheless, our findings are consistent with histological effects as well as the low velocity conduction observed in another study.

5.4 Analysis of the intra- and inter-observer variability of LGE-CMR measurements

Abstract

Late gadolinium enhancement cardiac magnetic resonance (LGE-CMR) imaging has been recently proposed to characterize left atrial (LA) anatomy and structural remodeling. LGE-CMR allows quantification of LA volume, shape (including the spherical remodeling) (Bisbal et al., 2013), location and extent of pre-ablation (Benito et al., 2018), and ablation-induced LA fibrosis (Bisbal et al., 2014). In general, a more profound atrial remodeling has been shown to predict worse outcomes after ablation procedures: patients with high LA scar burden (Marrouche et al., 2014), increased LA sphericity (Bisbal et al., 2013) and LA volume, and incomplete ablation lines (Bisbal et al., 2014), have increased AF recurrence risk. In order to allow widespread clinical application of these parameters, a thorough description of the intra- and inter-observer reproducibility and agreement of LGE-CMR measurements is needed. Also, the impact of observers experience on the measurement reproducibility and agreement needs to be assessed. The aims of this study were: 1) to provide a comprehensive assessment of intra- and inter-observer reproducibility and agreement of LGE-CMR parameters with direct application to AF ablation techniques; 2) to assess the impact of observer experience on the reproducibility and agreement of these measurements. One experienced and 1 non-experienced observer performed complete LGE-CMR data analysis, twice, in 40 randomly selected LGE-CMR examinations (20 pre- and 20 post-ablation). Two other experienced and 2 other non-experienced observers performed complete LGE-CMR data analysis in a subgroup of 30 patients (15 pre- and 15 post-ablation LGE-CMR) once. The geometric congruence of repeated LA segmentations from LGE-CMR was high, with maximal error $<5\text{mm}$ for intra-observer and $<8\text{mm}$ for inter-observer repeated measurements. The precision of scar location increased with extent of scar, and was higher for intra-observer experiments and post-ablation cases. Non-experienced observers performed equally well to experienced observers.

Data description

This work was performed in LGE-CMR data collected as part of the ALICIA (AiLlamente de venes pulmonares amb imatge de ressonancia - Isolation of pulmonary veins with magnetic resonance imaging; ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT02698631). In short, the ALICIA study was designed to assess the role of documenting the presence of LA fibrosis in guiding AF ablation. All patients recruited in this study had a LGE-CMR examination performed before AF ablation (to assess native LA fibrosis), and a follow-up LGE-CMR study performed 3 months after ablation (to assess ablation-induced LA fibrosis). From all the LGE-CMR examinations performed between October 2015 and February 2017 we randomly selected 20 pre-, and 20 post-ablation LGE-CMR with good or excellent image quality (according to visual assessment performed by an expert technician). The acquisition protocol has been previously reported (Benito et al., 2018; Bisbal et al., 2014). Briefly, images were acquired 20 min after an intravenous bolus injection of 0.2 mmol/kg gadobutrol (Gadovist, BayerShering) using either a 1.5 or a 3-Tesla magnetic resonance scanner (Magnetom Trio, Siemens Healthcare), and an ECG-gated sequence with respiratory navigator. Inversion time was set to suppress the healthy left ventricle myocardium.

Methods

Post-processing of the LGE-CMR data was performed using the ADAS-AF software (Galgo Medical S.L., Barcelona, Spain). Delineation of LA myocardium was achieved by manually tracking the mid-wall of the LA in each transverse LGE-CMR slice plane. The software then generated a 3D model of the LA from the slice-by-slice segmentation. The 3D reconstruction and the correctness of LA wall tracking was then checked by the operator and manually adjusted as necessary. On the final 3D model of the LA, the ADAS-AF software maps the LA fibrosis based on individual voxel intensity. Previously validated intensity threshold values were used for healthy and dense scar tissue classification (Benito et al., 2016): IIR (image intensity ratio, (Khurram et al., 2014)) >1.32 was considered dense fibrotic tissue.

Three experienced (defined as those with >12 months experience in LGE-CMR analysis, and who had performed >100 LGE-CMR segmentations) and 3 non-experienced (defined as those with <3 months experience in LGE-CMR analysis and <20 LGE-CMR analysis performed prior to this study)

Figure 5.13: Example of geometric inter-observer differences. Posterior view of a pair of 3D reconstructions of the left atrium, S and T , each performed by different observers. The left image depicts surface S with a color-code indicating the euclidean distance from each point in S to surface T . The right image depicts the opposite analysis: surface T and distances from each point in T to surface S . In this example, the maximal error occurs in the right carina.

observers were selected for this work. Before commencing this study, all non-experienced observers followed a brief training consisting in performing 10 LGE-CMR segmentation and interpretations (5 pre-, and 5 post-ablation) under direct supervision of an experienced observer. In addition, joint review sessions were held to ensure that each observer conducted LGE-CMR analyses in a similar way.

Two experiments were conducted:

1. *Intra-observer* reproducibility and agreement: One experienced (FA) and 1 non-experienced (ADM) observer performed complete LGE-CMR data analysis in all 40 patients, twice, in different days.
2. *Inter-observer* reproducibility and agreement: Two experienced observers (EB, FC) and 2 non-experienced (NE, JC) performed complete LGE-CMR data analysis in a subgroup of 30 patients (15 pre-ablation, and 15 post-ablation LGE-CMR), once.

Agreement between 3D models was quantified between LA segmentations extracted from the same LGE-CMR image (no registration was therefore required since the LA surfaces corresponding to the same image were aligned). In order to reduce any bias induced by manual clipping of the pulmonary veins (PV), left atrial appendage (LAA) and mitral valve (MV), clipping was performed following a previously described standardization protocol (Tobon-Gomez et al., 2015). This method semi-automatically clips the PV, LAA, and MV by finding the clipping planes at a fixed distance from the PV

Figure 5.14: Protocol for scar overlap quantification: two left atrial surfaces and their associated scars are extracted from the same LGE-CMR image. In this example, we show the 2 scar patterns by different colors for clarification purposes. Each scar is projected to the other surface and scar overlap is quantified in both surfaces using the Dice coefficient. Note that the projection slightly changes the scar patterns since the 2 surfaces are different (as they were acquired by two different observers). The final scar overlap value is obtained averaging the overlaps measured in the two surfaces

and LAA ostia. We computed these planes only once for each LGE-CMR image and reused them in all segmentations corresponding to the same image. After that, two types of analysis were performed: 1) shape differences were analysed by computing the mean and maximal surface to surface distance; and 2) spatial scar overlap was quantified between each pair of 3D models.

Given 2 surfaces $\{S, T\}$, the surface to surface distance, i.e. $d(S, T)$, is defined as the euclidean distance from every point in surface S to surface T . Note that d is not symmetric, i.e. $d(S, T) \neq d(T, S)$ (see Figure 5.13). We calculated the mean surface to surface distance, defined as:

$$D(S, T) = \text{mean}(\text{mean}[d(S, T)], \text{mean}[d(T, S)]) \quad (5.1)$$

and the Hausdorff surface to surface distance, defined as:

$$HD(S, T) = \max(\max[d(S, T)], \max[d(T, S)]) \quad (5.2)$$

that shows the maximum deviation between 2 shapes (maximal error).

To measure scar overlap we used *Dice* coefficient (Dice, 1945), that takes values from 0 (no overlap) to 1 (perfect overlap) and can be defined as follows:

$$Dice = \frac{|X \cap Y|}{|X| + |Y|} \quad (5.3)$$

where $|X \cap Y|$ corresponds to the overlapping area between scar X and scar Y , and $|X|$ and $|Y|$ are the areas of scar X and scar Y , respectively. Note that Dice coefficient quantifies spatial correlation of scar patches which is expected to worsen with small scar patches. Equally to surface-to-surface distance, overlap measurement is not symmetric. Scar overlapping (Dice) is computed in each of the two involved surfaces and the two metrics are subsequently averaged. An example of this procedure can be seen in Figure 5.14. We also computed the Accuracy of tissue type agreement, taking into account also the agreement in non-scar detection (which is generally high since, as said before, scar patches are typically small). We used customized code (Python, VTK) to compute all the measurements.

Results

Figure 5.15 shows an example of expert (a) and non-expert (b) intra- and inter-observer pairwise agreement with regard to scar location. Figure 5.16 shows result distributions of mean surface-to-surface distance (D) (top left), Hausdorff distance (HD) (top right), Dice (bottom left), and overall accuracy (bottom right) for the 4 experiments considered.

It can be seen that inter-observer variability is higher for all the metrics (bigger distances and lower Dice and Accuracy) for both expert and non-expert groups. The 3D LA surfaces were highly congruent, yielding an average difference between pairwise 3D shells of less than 1 mm in all cases. The maximal error between shells was found to be less than 4.6 mm for intra-observer measurements, and less than 7 mm for inter-observer analyses. Maximal surface differences were mainly located at the PV ostia. Overall scar overlap was high for all the cases but it highly depends on scar extension. Figure 5.17 shows the correlation between Dice and scar area. It can be seen how bigger scar areas correspond to bigger scar overlap and how, because scar burden increased after the ablation procedure, scar overlap is generally higher in post-ablation cases. The experience of the observers had no influence on scar location.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.15: Example of pair-wise scar overlap measurements for a given LGE-CMR image, for expert (a) and non-expert (b) observers. The initials of the observer performing the segmentation is displayed above each image, and the Dice coefficient measuring pairwise scar agreement appears below.

Figure 5.16: Congruence of LA 3D surface, mean (left) and maximum (center) surface to surface distance and Dice overlap coefficient (right). E-intra: expert intra-observer; E-inter: expert inter-observer; NE-intra: non-expert intra-observer; NE-inter: non-expert inter-observer.

Table 5.4: Statistics (mean \pm SD) of the intra- and inter-observer variability. D = mean surface to surface distance; HD = Hausdorff distance; E-intra = expert intra-observer; E-inter: expert inter-observer; NE-intra: non-expert intra-observer; NE-inter: non-expert inter-observer.

	D	HD	Dice	Accuracy
E-intra	0.570 \pm 0.191	3.887 \pm 1.375	0.773 \pm 0.149	0.979 \pm 0.016
E-inter	0.903 \pm 0.194	6.262 \pm 2.386	0.644 \pm 0.224	0.958 \pm 0.034
NE-intra	0.573 \pm 0.106	4.457 \pm 1.841	0.813 \pm 0.164	0.977 \pm 0.016
NE-inter	0.916 \pm 0.265	6.570 \pm 2.827	0.699 \pm 0.213	0.961 \pm 0.028

Discussion

In this work we assessed the reproducibility of LA and scar segmentations using the ADAS-AF software, but we consider that it would be extrapolated to other similar manual segmentations tools. We computed simple metrics based on euclidean distance and Dice overlap but it could be interesting to additionally quantify the error (in distance) between scars, not only the overlapping. Importantly, we only selected for analysis good quality LGE-CMR images (about one quarter of studies were excluded due to poor LGE-CMR image quality), so we did not report on the feasibility of LGE-CMR assessment of LA fibrosis.

Figure 5.17: Dice vs. scar area comparison. Pre-ablation cases are shown in blue and post-ablation cases in red.

The results of this study are important for the procedural skills of technicians and doctors involved in LGE-CMR evaluation of left atrial fibrosis for AF ablation and we have shown how non-experienced observers performed equally well to experienced observers. As a result, LGE-CMR assessment of LA measurements and scar extension can be applied in clinical practice after minimal training. Detailed studies should be performed regarding the impact of acquisition and measurement reproducibility on diagnostic accuracy, treatment outcome, and cost-efficiency of therapies initiated or continued based on imaging results.

5.5 Multi-modal data joint analysis

During this thesis we have also performed joint analysis of multi-modal data. We investigated the relation between radiofrequency (RF) catheter ablation parameters (power of the RF signal, catheter contact force, etc.) and the chronic lesion created, assessed by late gadolinium enhanced cardiac magnetic resonance (LGE-CMR) imaging. We have also developed new tools to consistently inspect the relation between the location of regions of slow conduction detected in electrophysiology (EP) studies and regions of hiper-enhancement in LGE-CMR images.

5.5.1 Analysis of the influence of radiofrequency ablation parameters on permanent lesion formation

Radiofrequency ablation is a common procedure to treat atrial fibrillation, where the objective is to electrically isolate some regions of the myocardium from others to avoid the transmission of abnormal electrical signals. This is done with a therapy electrophysiology catheter by delivering an RF signal (typically 30-40 W, 500 kHz) in the targeted regions. Ideally, the signal will create a permanent lesion that would prevent the reappearance of the abnormal electrical signals and terminate AF. There are many parameters involved in the process and naturally in its success. According to [Ganesan et al. \(2013\)](#) the long-term success rate ranges from 53.1% with a single procedure to almost 80% with multiple procedures. One of the reasons for this low success rate is the incomplete isolation of the PV due to punctate ablation leading to the presence of gaps in the lesion (scar or fibrous tissue). Clearly, incorrect RF ablation (e.g. when the catheter does not touch the LA wall) is a reason for incomplete PV isolation but also other involved parameters can favour the non formation of an effective lesion.

In this study we developed a framework for comparing RF ablation related parameters such as power of the signal, contact force, temperature and impedance with permanent and effective lesion formation. The task is challenging due to several reasons: during the ablation parameters are recorded at discrete locations (points, coordinates) and a method is needed to merge the information about the LA shape (previously extracted to help guiding the catheter) and the recorded points; additionally, there is LA remodelling due to the ablation procedure and to AF itself ([Kuppahally et al., 2010](#)) and therefore it is difficult to directly compare different atrial shapes; LA

segmentation from LGE-CMR is challenging due to insufficient image resolution to capture the thin atrial wall and the segmented LA shapes may appear even more different than they actually are due to segmentation errors. We used the SUM (Williams et al., 2017) because it allows us to directly compare atria with different shapes at different time-points and with different types of information.

Methods

The complete framework (with four main steps) can be seen in Fig. 5.18.

Figure 5.18: Complete framework. **A.** Extraction of the pre-ablation atrial shape and projection of the RF-ablation related parameters (automatically recorded during the ablation and saved in text files (the numbers shown here are unimportant)). In the figure, contact force values are shown on the LA surface. **B.** Extraction of the post-ablation atrial shape and LA wall tissue characterisation: binary classification into either scar or healthy tissue. **C.** SUM of the 3D LA shapes. **D.** Regional analysis and comparison of the two SUMs. The upper disk shows the two maps superimposed and the table shows results from the numerical analysis per region (numbers are irrelevant in this example). The small disk shows the regional division of the LA.

1. Acquisition of RF-ablation related parameters. Previous to the ablation procedure, and with the aim of helping guiding the catheter, all patients undergo an image study (Computed Tomography (CT) or CMR). The anatomical information is obtained by delineating the LA shape followed by some pre-process (smooth and mesh correction) in order to eliminate artefacts due to imaging. During the intervention, the mesh is imported into the navigation system and aligned with the current view by rigid registration (rotation and translation). Using the registration matrix it is possible to realign the original mesh and the recorded points afterwards. During the ablation the following parameters are saved into the system with a sampling period of

17 ms: position of the catheter tip, power, contact force, temperature and impedance. All this information is projected onto the LA mesh as follows: for each ablation-related sample we find its closest point (vertex) in the mesh. It is noticeable that several ablation-related points may lie on the same LA mesh point. In that situation information is accumulated in the corresponding vertex. Accordingly, vertices of the LA mesh without projected ablation-related points have an assigned value of 0 and are not used in the numerical analysis. The output of this stage is a LA mesh showing the pre-ablation LA anatomy with that information projected (see Fig. 5.18A).

2. Tissue characterization of the post ablated LA. The LA wall is manually segmented from a LGE-CMR imaging study performed 3 months after the ablation. Binary tissue classification (scar or healthy) is then performed according to the method presented by Benito et al. (2016): Local Image Intensity Ratio (IIR) is calculated as the ratio between the pixel and the mean blood pool intensities. The authors established thresholds based on healthy volunteers and post-ablation patients: an $IIR \leq 1.20$ identifies normal atrial tissue, and an $IIR > 1.32$ identifies dense scarring (see Fig. 5.18B).
3. Standardised Unfold Map (SUM). SUMs of the 2 2D LA surfaced previously acquired are obtained as follows:
 - a) Mesh standardisation: the PVs and the left atrial appendage (LAA) are semiautomatically clipped. The algorithm requires to manually place a seed close to the ending point of each PV and the LAA. After that, the PVs and LAA are automatically clipped at a distance of the ostium that can be set by the user. Also the mitral valve (MV) is automatically clipped using the information of the placed seeds. We decided to clip the LAA because it is not directly related to PVI.
 - b) Surface registration of the standardised atria obtained before to the SUM template. This is done by a non-rigid registration based on currents (Durrleman et al., 2014) after an initial affine registration.
 - c) Information mapping to the disk: the MV is mapped to the boundary of the disk and the PV and LAA holes are mapped to predefined holes within the disk. Let us name these maps *ablation-SUM* and *scar-SUM*.

4. Analysis and comparison of the ablation and scar SUMs. For comparing these two maps we propose the following:
 - a) Use the parcellation provided by the SUM to evaluate RF-ablation related parameters in each region of the *ablation-SUM*. As we are interested in evaluating the success of PVI we focus in regions representing the surroundings of each PV. For each vein, its surroundings are divided in four quadrants, thus 16 regions are analysed. We compute the mean and total values of power, contact force and temperature in each SUM region.
 - b) Localise gaps in the *scar-SUM*. For doing this we follow a strategy similar to the one we presented in Garcia et al. (2015): we define the *isolating path* as the scar-path that encircles a PV with the minimum amount of gap. We then identify the regions of the SUM where a gap is present. If the gap is less than 10% of the isolating path is ignored.
 - c) Correlate the information about the gaps (yes/no) with the ablation parameters in all regions: mean and total power, contact force and temperature. With regard to the impedance it is interesting to analyse the impedance drop. In this initial version of the framework we project all the samples to the LA mesh losing the time reference. We need to take into account the particular temporal instant in order to be able of analysing impedance drops. This could be done complementing the framework adding temporal information but it was left to future work.

Results

We applied the proposed method to 8 real cases. The RF catheter used was the Thermocool SmartTouch⁸ and the ablation information was acquired with CARTO-3. Anatomical information was incorporated from pre-interventional CT or CMR images and the LA shape was extracted from the

⁸Biosense Webster Inc, Diamond Bar, CA

DICOM images using a research software (ADAS-AF⁹) or CartoMERGE in the case of CT images. The number of ablation-related samples in our data was $98,821 \pm 3,302$ samples. Regarding the *scar-SUM*, manual segmentations of the LA wall surface were extracted also using the ADAS-AF software and tissue classification was performed according to Benito et al. (2016) as explained before. For the generation of the SUMs we decided to keep a PV and LAA length of 3 mm in all the cases. The complete framework (pre-processing, mapping and post-processing) was coded in Python using the VTK library. We also used reMESH Attene and Falcidieno (2006) for correcting mesh imperfections.

Fig. 5.19 and Table 5.5 show the SUMs generated for one patient and its numerical analysis.

Figure 5.19: Example of the 2 SUMs generated for one patient. From left to right: template with region labels; *ablation-SUM* showing in this case the information about contact force; *scar-SUM* showing the segmented scar (magenta) and the detected gaps (yellow).

The power of the signal was not studied since the recommended power (40 W) was used for all cases. Nevertheless, we found that the mean value is slightly inferior because there are growing and decreasing slopes when passing from 0 W to 40 W and vice versa. With relation to the temperature it can be seen that it is significantly lower than the typically target temperature (i.e. 50-55 °C). This is due to the fact that the ablation was done with an irrigated catheter (in order to induce a deeper lesion) which is a type of cooled tip ablation Thomas et al. (2004); Yamane et al. (2000). In the example (Fig. 5.19), there are two gaps: one in the left superior PV (LSPV) and the other one in the right superior PV (RSPV). Results in Table 5.5 suggest that the gap in region 10 can be due to low CF even though

⁹ADAS, Galgo Medical SL. Barcelona, Spain

the ablation time is quite high. We could also hypothesise that the gap in region 11 corresponds to an area insufficiently ablated (see *ablation-SUM* in that region). If we compare regions 17 and 18 we can see that the two regions were ablated during a similar period of time but in region 17 the mean CF and mean power were lower than in region 18. This fact could explain why we see a gap in region 17 and not in region 18. Likewise, if we compare regions 19 and 20 that were also ablated during a similar period of time, we observe again that the mean CF and mean power are lower in the region where there is a gap (20). However, we observe that in other regions good scar patterns were obtained with lower CF, power and in less time. Examples of efficient ablations can be seen in regions 13, 16 and 18 where a good scar pattern was created in a short period of time (see Fig. 5.19).

Table 5.5: Some results from the numerical analysis of the example in Fig. 5.19.

Region	Mean Power (W)	Mean Contact Force (g)	Mean Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Mean Time (min)	Gap?
9	37.56	5.29	41.98	2.60	Too small
10	39.32	3.85	42.14	5.05	Yes
11	34.99	9.18	41.37	1.12	Yes
12	38.49	7.40	41.53	2.41	No
13	39.33	6.10	42.02	0.36	No
14	36.79	3.61	42.74	1.33	No
15	36.17	5.64	41.30	2.17	No
16	36.65	4.87	40.01	0.17	No
17	37.56	4.73	41.57	1.12	Yes
18	39.93	6.42	42.12	1.28	No
19	38.66	7.36	41.49	3.25	No
20	35.83	6.76	41.68	3.15	Yes
21	39.96	4.22	42.41	2.23	No
22	38.77	6.87	41.92	2.17	No
23	35.13	9.46	40.16	1.37	No
24	39.88	4.47	42.45	0.33	No

We compared the numerical analysis of all patients trying to find common patterns relating the parameters and the presence or absence of anatomical gaps but statistically significant differences were not found (see Table 5.6). We also analysed the influence of the ablation time: we investigated whether it is more effective to ablate during a shorter period of time with a higher contact force or with lower contact force during a longer period of time but there was not any consistent pattern. Even more, unexpectedly, we found that regions with gaps were ablated (in average) much time and with a higher CF (Fig. 5.20).

Figure 5.20: Example of pair of SUMs generated: the first row shows *ablation-SUM* (with mapped contact force, temperature and power information) and the second row their associated *scar-SUM*. Each column corresponds to a different patient.

Table 5.6: Numerical analysis results: comparison between regions with and without gap. Shown is the mean \pm standard error of power, contact force, temperature, number of CARTO samples and time.

	Power (W)	Force (g)	Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	# CARTO samples	Time (min)
No gap	34.74 ± 1.88	7.82 ± 1.00	39.55 ± 0.94	5035.09 ± 1566.39	1.43 ± 0.44
Gap	34.95 ± 1.34	8.01 ± 0.80	39.35 ± 0.67	7550.80 ± 1857.57	2.14 ± 0.53

We could not identify optimal values for ablation parameters from our experiments. Some potential reasons are: (1) The dataset is too small for extracting well founded conclusions; (2) The LA wall is very thin and its segmentation and posterior scar detection is complicated. (3) Patients with AF may have natural fibrosis (not induced by the ablation) that would be classified as scar in the tissue classification process. It would be convenient to perform tissue classification previous to the RF-ablation in order to be able to differentiate between natural and ablation induced fibrosis. For this study we did not have access to the pre-ablation images but we plan to enrich the method by including this information in the future; (4) Scar induced by the ablation can remodel after some time due to natural tissue recovery.

5.5.2 Inspection of the relation between regions of slow electrical conduction and regions of scar in the LA

We have developed a registration-based framework to find spatial correlation between electroanatomical information acquired with invasive mapping

system (e.g. CARTO¹⁰) and tissue information acquired with LGE-MRI. The problem is challenging since, even corresponding to the same patient, both LA shapes are typically very dissimilar due to the different acquisition modalities. This is an ongoing project (data acquisition is not finished) but preliminary results showed a significant relation between the location of regions of slow electrical conduction and regions of scar ($p < 0.0004$).

Methods

The overview of the proposed method can be seen in Figure 5.21.

Figure 5.21: Scheme of multi-modal data analysis. LA anatomy and tissue type in the LA wall is extracted from LGE-CMR data. A reconstructed EAM is obtained from CARTO points. Spatial correspondence of CARTO points and LGE-CMR derived LA shape is obtained using our registration-based approach. LGE-CMR = late gadolinium enhanced cardiac magnetic resonance. EAM = electroanatomical map.

LA segmentation from LGE-CMR was performed manually using ADAS-

¹⁰Biosense Webster Inc, Diamond Bar, CA

AF¹¹), Image Intensity Ratio (IIR, (Khurram et al., 2014)) was computed on the LA surface and tissue was classified according to the thresholds proposed by Benito et al. (2016): $IIR \leq 1.20$ was considered normal healthy tissue, $1.20 < IIR < 1.32$ was considered interstitial fibrosis (or border zone (BZ)) and $IIR > 1.32$ denoted dense scar. On the other hand, EAM data was extracted from the CARTO mapping system, including a reconstructed LA surface mesh. CARTO points were firstly projected onto the EAM surface mesh by closest point approximation. After that, both LA surface meshes (LGE-CMR-related and CARTO-related) were standardised by semi-automatically clipping the PVs, LAA and MV as proposed by Tobon-Gomez et al. (2015). Then, both standardised meshes were affinely and non-rigidly (using currents (Durrleman et al., 2014)) registered to a LA template mesh. Having both meshes in the template space, CARTO points were projected from the EAM registered surface mesh to the LGE-CMR-related mesh. Four examples of point-to-point spatial correlation found using our approach can be seen in Figure 5.22. It can be observed how red points on the left (corresponding to EAM) were projected to the same anatomical location on the right (corresponding to LA segmented from LGE-CMR) even if the two LA surfaces were very different. Note for instance the different PV ostium sizes.

Figure 5.22: Four examples of point-to-point spatial correspondence between LA segmentations from LGE-CMR and EAMs. Each specific CARTO point is shown in red. The LA surface meshes were consistently divided into 12 regions (shown with different colors here).

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Results

Preliminary results were obtained using data from 10 AF patients with median number of CARTO points (after excluding points from the PVs and LAA) equal to 302.0 points (min = 83 points, max = 1320 points). In total, 4311 points were analysed. Comparison of IIR and conduction velocity (estimated as in Iglesias et al. (2017)) can be seen in Figure 5.23. Using the 1.20 threshold, 540 points were classified as scar and a two-sample t-test revealed significant differences across the two distributions, $p = 4 \times 10^{-5}$. After applying the 1.32 threshold only 157 points were classified as scar. Differences between the two groups (dense scar and the rest) were also found statistically significant ($p = 6 \times 10^{-4}$).

Figure 5.23: Comparison of normalized image intensity and velocity. Points projected to areas of different IIR range are shown with different colors: IIR < 1.20 (green), $1.20 < \text{IIR} < 1.32$ (blue), and IIR > 1.32 (purple). IIR = Image Intensity Ratio.

Our preliminary findings suggest that areas of scar correlate well with areas of slow conduction while areas of healthy tissue can exhibit varying electrical conduction characteristics.

Conclusions

This thesis has developed new approaches to investigate the pathophysiology and progression of atrial fibrillation.

Imaging of atrial scar with LGE-MRI is controversial but we have shown how it is a reproducible finding, under appropriate imaging conditions (i.e., imaging should be performed at least 20 min post-gadolinium-based contrast agent injection). However, the clinical implications of these findings remain to be established in the absence of a simple correlation with arrhythmia outcome. We have developed a fully automatic LA segmentation technique that reduces the workload of manual segmentations. However, new techniques based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have very recently emerged, with improved accuracy results, that would lead segmentation tasks in the near future. CNN-based methods have shown to be able to accurately segment the LA from LGE-MRI in a few minutes or even seconds after offline training. We consider that this will contribute to the investigation of new scar detection methods (which needs further validation) since until now, the segmentation of the LA was a bottleneck in the process. Currently, there is no consensus about the most suitable scar segmentation technique (apart from manual approaches) with a significant disparity between the state of the art in clinical environments and the state of the art in technical research. In clinical investigations, scar detection is based on thresholds (computed in very diverse way) even though threshold-based methods tend to be centre- and vendor-specific and have lower reproducibility than other more complex algorithms (e.g. deep-learning based).

Inspection of 3D surfaces is time-consuming, requiring several rotations to fully inspect a given surface, and flattening methods highly simplify visualisation tasks. Moreover, if the 2D representation is standardised, it allows direct comparison between different shapes. In this thesis, we have proposed a novel flattening technique for the LA that maps any LA to a common 2D template. The method is fast, does not lose information and it emphasizes regional interpretability by confining anatomical regions to predefined locations in the 2D map avoiding undesired displacements attributable to global flattening methods. Our method can be used in several contexts: to compare multi-modal data from the same patient (e.g. tissue type from LGE-MRI and voltage from EAM); in longitudinal studies, for example to inspect changes due to AF progression or the effect of an ablation procedure (comparison of pre- and post-ablation tissue type in the LA wall); or to perform population analysis (e.g. inspect the regional distribution of fibrosis).

There are many uncertainty sources in the inspection of PVI ablation procedures. We have contributed to reduce that uncertainty in two ways: first, providing a consistent definition of ablation gap and a reproducible method to quantify it; and second, developing a new metric that combines several threshold-based scar segmentations. Our method also outputs the regional location of the gaps potentially reducing procedural time if an ablation redo is required, and facilitating investigation of the relation between anatomical and electrical gaps. We showed the suitability of the proposed method to quantify lesion completeness/incompleteness after PVI and it could therefore be used to compare novel ablation catheters or techniques at full vein isolation efficiency in a consistent and fair way. Our method could also be used to detect target ablation regions, previously to a redo procedure, favouring its planning and potentially lowering its duration.

During this thesis, and thanks to the close collaboration with different electrophysiologists and clinicians, we were involved in several clinical investigations. We developed computational tools that were used to: (1) observe that in patients with AF, native fibrosis is preferentially located at the posterior wall and floor around the antrum of the left inferior pulmonary vein; (2) the geometric agreement of repeated LA manual segmentations and posterior scar detection based on thresholds is high and LGE-CMR assessment of LA measurements and scar extension may be applied in clinical practice after minimal training; (3) areas of slow electrical conduction correlate well with areas of atrial scar.

6.1 Future research lines

For future work, we plan to extend the Fast Regional Flattening framework proposed in Chapter 3 to LA with different number of veins. Currently, it can only be applied to 4-vein LA and further investigation is required to find a common reference template that could be used for all possible PV configurations. Additionally, we believe that the method could be extended to a whole-heart (four chamber) flattening of the heart, simply requiring the adaptation of the template (*boudary* and *regional constraints*) to the whole-heart anatomy.

Novel intra-cavitary high resolution mapping systems will allow detailed inspection of electrical activity in the left atria. The acquisition of realistic EAM has the potential to provide insight into AF sources, to facilitate ablation planning and to improve the prediction of ablation outcome. We

Figure 6.1: Inspection of RF parameters

plan to benefit from them to improve the knowledge about the relation between electrical activity in the heart and the type of tissue observed with LGE-MRI data, and to further investigate the relation between radiofrequency ablation parameters and electrical reconnection sites identified in a redo procedure. Related to the latter, we have developed a preliminary registration-based framework. Figure 6.1 (a) shows two EAM corresponding to a first ablation (left), and corresponding redo (right). Points of redo ablation correspond to regions where reconnection was found (electrical gaps) and its position is estimated in the first ablation map to allow inspection of the RF parameters used the first time (Figure 6.1 (b)). However, more realistic and reliable EAM are required to properly accomplish this investigation.

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Curriculum Vitae

Marta Núñez García received her M.Sc. degree in Telecommunications Engineering from the Universidade de Vigo in 2012 and her M.Sc. degree in Computer Vision and Artificial Intelligence from the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona in 2013. She joined PhySense research group (Universitat Pompeu Fabra) and started her Ph.D. under the supervision of Dr. Oscar Camara and Dr. Constantine Butakoff in 2014. During this period, her main research interest was shape analysis and parameterisation of the left atrium in the context of atrial fibrillation. She developed computational algorithms and tools to analyse multi-modal medical images such as MRI, LGE-MRI, electroanatomical maps or echocardiography data.

Publications

Journal papers

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Conference papers

1. **Nuñez-Garcia, M.**, Zhuang X., Sanroma G., Li L., Xu L., Butakoff C., Camara O. 2018. Left atrial segmentation combining multi-atlas whole heart labeling and shape-based atlas selection. In *International Workshop on Statistical Atlases and Computational Models of the Heart (STACOM)*. Accepted.
2. Mill J., Olivares A., Silva E., Genua I., Fernandez A, Aguado A, **Nuñez-Garcia, M.**, Potter T., Freixa X., Camara O. 2018. Joint analysis of personalized in-silico haemodynamics and shape descriptors of the left atrial appendage. In *International Workshop on Statistical Atlases and Computational Models of the Heart (STACOM)*. Accepted.
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